

Exploring V2X in 5G networks: A comprehensive survey of location-based services in hybrid scenarios[☆]

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ABSTRACT

Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) communications are constrained by both 3GPP technical specifications, as well as by country-specific spectrum regulations. The world's largest economies, such as the USA, EU and China have self-imposed regulations regarding the specific bandwidths and central spectrum frequencies where both safety and non-safety related V2X communication services are allowed to occur (always aligned with the aforementioned 3GPP technical specifications). Although the channels used for safety, non-safety, and control packets differ, what all of these countries have in common is that V2X shall occur mostly on New Radio Unlicensed (NR-U) spectrum, i.e., by means of private networks. A specific bandwidth in the public spectrum is also available, but since public spectrum is purchased through auctions, it is quite common the case that one particular operator will own the entirety of this spectrum, leading to a monopoly in V2X operations. Besides, this public spectrum is quite limited in bandwidth. This of course includes all of the Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITS) services, even location-based services, such as the ones that require the usage of positioning technologies, like autonomous vehicles, that require said services in order to support complex maneuvers and cooperative driving. Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS) such as GPS or Galileo, currently already offer high-accuracy location to vehicles. However, this form of stand-alone position estimation of the vehicle has several drawbacks, as the information is constrained to the individual vehicle and not shared with others in a secure manner. This exchange of position information between other entities (not only vehicles, but also other infrastructure nodes) is vital for actions such as cooperative maneuvers and to counter loss of satellite sight (e.g., when entering a tunnel). Taking these facts into consideration, it is therefore expected that in the mid to long-term, municipalities and highways will possess dedicated private 5G networks for V2X operations with the aim of offering a plethora of vehicular services, including positioning ones. Since the existent scientific literature lacks an integrated analysis of precise positioning services for ITS in 5G private networks, we propose in this paper, to provide a comprehensive review connecting these diverse elements, examining the role of 5G private networks in transmitting positioning messages in V2X scenarios. Additionally, the paper shall explore hybrid positioning systems that combine 5G and GNSS technologies, illustrating their potential to enhance V2X communications. This study offers a roadmap for the evolution of ITS and V2X communications by showcasing current trends and identifying areas for further research.

1. Introduction

The automotive sector is undergoing a significant transformation driven by technological advancements in Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITS), that permit vehicles to support advanced actions such as cooperative maneuvers, platooning and lane merging, which are

imperative in highly automated driving systems. The automotive industry is characterized by its stringent safety concerns, so having cars offering these advanced actions will require them to be capable of efficiently communicate and exchange data and other control information between themselves and the surrounding infrastructure and sensors. And by efficiently, this means rapidly, i.e., with extreme low

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latency, and with high reliability, through a Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) communication system. 5G networks offer promising support for V2X communication in this context. However, most studies focus on public 5G networks managed by Mobile Network Operators (MNO)s, leaving a gap in understanding how private 5G networks can address the specific demands of V2X systems, particularly for autonomous driving. Public 5G networks, while capable, often face challenges such as resource congestion and unpredictable latency due to their shared nature. And although 3GPP has pre-defined V2X network slices that can segregate resources, so they can be dedicated to vehicular communications, an MNO is unlikely to possess the necessary dedicated bandwidth that such a slice could potentially require.

This paper addresses this gap by focusing on private 5G networks and their potential to support cooperative localization, an essential requirement for V2X applications. Cooperative localization allows vehicles to share precise position data and surrounding infrastructure, enhancing situational awareness and improving safety. This process combines Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS) data with relative 5G measurements to ensure accurate positioning, even in environments where GNSS is unreliable, such as urban canyons or tunnels. Moreover, it is important to mention that GNSS only offers high-accuracy location estimates when using correction services provided by a third-party (which can be public and free data, as Galileo offer this service). This correction data is typically sent out by a satellite to be then processed in the car satellite receiver. This traditional solution has two problems: first the latency of the correction signal transited by the satellite; and second, car manufacturers avoid having devices embedded in the vehicle with high processing capabilities. Fortunately, 3GPP took this into consideration and current 5G architecture is designed to be able to send out post-processed GNSS correction data directly to the vehicle. Thus, by integrating real-time GNSS corrections with 5G-based positioning, private 5G networks can deliver the precision required for location-based tasks like obstacle avoidance. This paper explores strategies for leveraging private 5G networks to overcome these challenges, providing a step closer to the realization of fully autonomous driving.

Fig. 1. Illustration of a 5G-V2X ecosystem with GNSS satellites, 5G communication tower, and autonomous vehicles.

As shown in Fig. 1, the 5G-V2X connected ecosystem contains several components such as GNSS satellites, a 5G communication tower, and autonomous vehicles. This configuration shows how private 5G networks can enable data exchange and improve localization accuracy for autonomous driving, particularly in complex urban environments. This survey investigates the necessary technologies to achieve this ecosystem.

One of the significant challenges identified is the unreliability of public 5G networks for V2X communication.

Public networks must accommodate a wide range of users, leading to resource contention and fluctuating latency, which can critically impact safety-related applications like cooperative driving. Timely delivery of Cooperative Awareness Messages (CAM) and Distributed Environment Notification Messages (DENM) is essential for road safety, yet public networks struggle to maintain the consistent performance required for real-time communication. In contrast, private 5G networks offer exclusive network capacity and guaranteed Quality of Service (QoS), explicitly tailored to V2X applications. This paper suggests that private 5G networks are better suited for V2X, and offer the flexibility to design customized communication infrastructures optimized for the specific needs of ITS.

Another significant issue is positioning accuracy, a crucial factor for autonomous vehicles, which public 5G networks do not address sufficiently. While GNSS, such as GPS and Galileo, are the standards for vehicle positioning, their performance is often compromised in complex environments. Hybrid positioning techniques that integrate GNSS and 5G-based localization are proposed, combining terrestrial and non-terrestrial systems to provide sub-meter accuracy in critical vehicular applications. This hybrid approach holds significant potential to improve autonomous vehicle operations in challenging environments like tunnels or dense urban areas.

The paper also examines how private 5G networks can address issues like packet delivery rate, bandwidth limitations, and latency, which are crucial for maintaining cooperative localization in V2X communication. Delays or packet loss can lead to vehicle miscommunication, increasing the risk of collisions or unsafe driving maneuvers. By providing guaranteed packet delivery and real-time GNSS corrections, private 5G networks can ensure continuous and reliable localization, even in scenarios where GNSS signals are weak or disrupted. This opens the door to ultra-reliable V2X communication, vital for deploying autonomous vehicles in complex environments.

The instantaneous advancement of 5G technology has opened new possibilities for V2X communication, setting the stage for transformative improvements in vehicle safety, traffic efficiency, and autonomous driving systems. Current studies underscore the potential of 5G-enabled V2X systems across various use cases, yet there is a notable gap regarding high-precision localization, which is essential for real-time V2X scenarios. Foundational work, such as that by [1], thoroughly discusses V2X use cases and the architectural needs for 5G support but does not delve into the specialized requirements for accurate, reliable positioning. Similarly, [2] addresses the integration challenges within 5G V2X from a business and regulatory standpoint but offers limited insight into technical enhancements for localization. As V2X applications increasingly rely on precise and continuous location data, these broad perspectives highlight a clear need for research targeting the localization challenges inherent in V2X contexts.

Technical surveys on 5G infrastructure and standards for V2X, like those by [3] (see Table 1), explore the landscape of 5G V2X technology comprehensively. Yet, they do not specifically address how dedicated network configurations (such as private 5G networks) might enhance V2X localization. While these studies establish an essential foundation for standardization and infrastructure, they leave open the question of whether more specialized network setups could support the precise positioning required for safety-critical V2X functions. Other studies on platoon cooperation in V2X, such as the work by [4], propose valuable solutions for intra-platoon communication through resource allocation

Table 1
Summary of Existing 5G V2X Studies and Proposed Differentiation with Private Network for Localization.

Study Title	Focus Area	Limitations	Differentiation with Private Network for Localization
Use Cases, Requirements, and Design Considerations for 5G V2X [1]	V2X use cases, design for automated driving, architectural guidance	Broad overview, lacks focus on precise localization	Uses private 5G to enhance V2X localization precision, improving reliability and network control.
A Business and Legislative Perspective of V2X and Mobility Applications in 5G Networks [2]	Business models, legislative challenges in V2X for 5G	Business-oriented, lacks technical localization framework	Highlights private 5G to provide dedicated localization resources, ensuring better accuracy and latency.
A Survey of 5G Technology Evolution, Standards, and Infrastructure Associated With Vehicle-to-Everything Communications by Internet of Vehicles [3]	Evolution and standards of 5G for V2X, technical issues	Broad survey, limited on localization specifics	Proposes private 5G for high-precision localization, offering capabilities not available in public networks.
Platoon Cooperation in Cellular V2X Networks for 5G and Beyond [4]	Resource allocation and power management for platoon V2X	Focuses on platoon use cases, lacks broader V2X localization support	Extends private 5G for broader V2X localization in complex scenarios beyond platooning.
Security of 5G-V2X: Technologies, Standardization, and Research Directions [5]	Security in 5G-V2X, focusing on reliability and latency	High-level security approach, minimal focus on localization security	Adds secure localization in private 5G for V2X, crucial for safety-sensitive applications.

and power management. However, these insights are limited primarily to platoon-based use cases, overlooking the broader potential for high-accuracy localization in varied and complex V2X scenarios that exist beyond structured platoons. Security remains a concern in 5G V2X research, as underscored by works like [5], emphasizing the importance of secure data exchange in V2X. Yet, these studies rarely discuss security integration within high-precision localization, where reliable positioning is crucial to the safety and success of V2X applications. In safety-critical contexts, the precision of localization must be paired with security to prevent disruptions or inaccuracies in the data on which these systems depend.

Given these gaps, this research focuses on leveraging private 5G networks as a tailored solution for supporting high-precision localization in V2X environments. Unlike public 5G infrastructure, a private 5G network provides dedicated resource allocation, precise control, and low-latency communication, all critical for achieving the accuracy and responsiveness needed in real-time V2X localization. By optimizing network configurations specifically for these positioning needs, this study aims to enhance the reliability and security of V2X localization. This approach does not merely address the technical limitations seen in broader V2X frameworks and offers a practical, scalable foundation for the next generation of ITS.

A literature review was conducted to ensure this research is grounded in the latest advancements and addresses critical gaps. The review targeted studies on deploying private 5G networks for V2X communication and hybrid positioning methods that integrate GNSS and 5G technologies. Databases such as IEEE Xplore, ACM Digital Library, and

ScienceDirect were searched using carefully selected terms related to private 5G, V2X, hybrid positioning, and associated challenges like latency, interference reduction, and network reliability. Only peer-reviewed studies with clear methodologies were included to maintain academic rigor. The review identified common themes, challenges, and solutions, particularly in how private 5G networks enhance cooperative localization, improve network reliability, and address positioning challenges in complex environments. It also highlighted the potential of hybrid GNSS-5G methods to overcome localization issues, especially in urban multipath scenarios. By synthesizing the existing literature, this review revealed critical gaps that this paper seeks to address, focusing on integrating private 5G networks with V2X communication and advanced positioning technologies for autonomous vehicles.

As the V2X advances, supporting the demands of autonomous driving requires connectivity and exact and low-latency communication. The 5G network includes potential congestion and fluctuating latency, which can compromise autonomous systems' reliability and safety. Private 5G networks, on the other hand, emerge as a promising alternative by providing dedicated resources that better meet the exacting requirements of V2X applications. Their role in enhancing safety and reliability in V2X communication is reassuring for the future of autonomous driving.

This document examines how private 5G networks can address the precise localization and communication requirements of V2X systems, especially in contexts demanding high accuracy and low latency. The introduction establishes the scope, highlighting the transformative potential of 5G advancements for autonomous driving and underscores the need for dedicated private networks to enhance V2X localization. The Chapter 2 explores V2X communications as a foundation for autonomous driving, focusing on the critical infrastructure required for various autonomy levels. It emphasizes the role of Cellular Vehicle-to-Everything (C-V2X) and ITS in ensuring safe, coordinated vehicle operations. This foundational analysis frames the potential impact of private 5G networks on vehicle coordination and localization. Chapter 3 addresses V2X localization techniques, analyzing both 5G and GNSS methods. This chapter discusses the limitations of GNSS in urban environments and highlights the enhanced accuracy that private 5G can provide, especially for real-time V2X applications. Emphasizing precision, it argues for the distinct advantages of private 5G in achieving reliable, high-accuracy localization. Then Chapter 4 contrasts public and private 5G, focusing on the limitations of public networks, including resource contention and inconsistent latency, which hinder safety-critical V2X applications. This chapter suggests that private 5G with unlicensed spectrum can more reliably support real-time communication needs through dedicated, low-latency environments. Finally, Chapter 5 outlines research directions and proposes private 5G as a scalable infrastructure to address V2X's evolving demands. Exploring specialized configurations positions private 5G networks as a promising path for future autonomous transportation systems, meeting the rigorous requirements of precision, security, and reliability. It explores the lessons learned throughout the research.

2. V2X communication and autonomous driving

Autonomous vehicle operation depends on sophisticated communication networks that enable fast, reliable, and seamless data exchange with surrounding systems. V2X technology, mainly C-V2X, is instrumental in meeting these requirements across different levels of autonomy, from driver assistance to full automation, as defined by the Society of Automotive Engineers¹ (SAE).

Autonomous driving refers to the ability of a vehicle to operate independently without the need for human intervention. It is a promising application driven by advancing technology, including

¹ <https://www.sae.org/>.

artificial intelligence and advanced sensors [6]. Autonomous driving involves using complex systems such as sensors (e.g., cameras, radar, and lidar), data processing algorithms, and control systems to enable a vehicle to identify and respond to its surrounding environment. These systems collect real-time information about traffic, obstacles, pedestrians, and other road elements, allowing the vehicle to make informed decisions about acceleration, braking, changing lanes, and other maneuvers.

Autonomous vehicles cannot rely only on their onboard sensors, and to operate effectively, they need robust infrastructure with advanced communication capabilities that support fast, reliable, and low-latency data exchanges with surrounding systems. V2X technology, particularly C-V2X, meets these demands by providing multiple modes of interaction that enhance safety, efficiency, and user experience across different levels of vehicle autonomy.

With this in mind, Society of Automotive Engineers (SAE) defined different levels of autonomous driving, classified according to the degree of human intervention required and autonomy of a vehicle, known as Automation Levels, [7]. Here are the primary levels of automation:

- **Level 0 - No Automation:** The driver controls the vehicle. There is no automation present.
- **Level 1 - Driver Assistance:** The vehicle has adaptive cruise control (ACC) and steering assistance features. However, the driver retains complete vehicle control and must always be involved in driving.
- **Level 2 - Partial automation:** The vehicle can control acceleration, braking, and steering in certain situations. However, the driver is still responsible for supervising the driving environment and must be prepared to regain vehicle control when necessary.
- **Level 3 - Conditional Automation:** The vehicle can control driving under predefined conditions. The driver can disengage from driving tasks and perform other activities but must be prepared to resume control when the system requests.
- **Level 4 - High automation:** The vehicle can be autonomous in almost all conditions but may require driver intervention in exceptional situations. The driver can choose not to be involved in driving in certain situations.
- **Level 5 - Full automation:** The vehicle is fully autonomous and does not require human intervention. There is no need for a steering wheel, pedals, or any manual controls.

In order to help the developments and architecture of these systems, the European Union (EU), legislation has created specific rules related to the automotive spectrum and applications that follow particular guidelines. In the context of connected vehicles and ITS, there are two distinct groups: critical and non-critical systems. The EU has defined specific spectrum bands for critical ITS systems. In the public spectrum band, the 2.6 GHz range is reserved for the use of it. This frequency band enables the implementation of C-V2X communication services for applications requiring fast response times and reliable communications in safety-critical situations. In addition, the EU has also designated the 5.9 GHz spectrum band for critical ITS communications on a private basis [8]. This study intends to showcase the usage of this spectrum band to send messages containing precise localization with the objective of a full collaboration to achieve level five of automation.

2.1. Cellular vehicle-to-everything (C-V2X)

C-V2X is a sophisticated wireless communication technology that enables vehicles to interact with diverse objects and systems in their environment, such as Vehicle-to-Vehicle (V2V), Vehicle-to-Infrastructure (V2I), Vehicle-to-Pedestrian (V2P), and Vehicle-to-Network (V2N). It uses the same network infrastructure as smartphones and other cellular devices, enabling communication between cars and other road users, pedestrians, and infrastructure (such as traffic lights and road signs). Based on LTE and 5G cellular technologies, C-V2X

utilizes the same network infrastructure as cellular devices, allowing vehicles to communicate with each other and external elements like traffic signals and road signs. Each mode of C-V2X communication supports specific applications. For instance, V2V enables essential data sharing for collision avoidance, V2I optimizes traffic flow, V2P enhances pedestrian safety, and V2N connects vehicles to the cloud for continuous updates, as shown in Fig. 2. These capabilities open new possibilities for C-V2X to enhance autonomous driving functionality, which requires real-time coordination with the environment. International standards such as ITS-G5, DSRC, and C-V2X have been established to support consistent and effective communication across diverse V2X applications. Each standard addresses specific V2X requirements, optimizing data exchanges to achieve high performance across latency, reliability, and interoperability metrics essential for autonomous driving.

The C-V2X is a crucial technology for developing connected and autonomous cars. It can increase traffic flow efficiency, enhance the travel experience by enabling new services and apps, and boost road safety.

In [9], it is shown that there are efforts by 3GPP to standardize the relation between the C-V2X communications and the autonomous driving application. The study aims to simplify the 3GPP documentation and its role in achieving Level-5 autonomous driving. The result from these standards will boost the original equipment manufacturers (OEMs) and regions such as the USA and EU, decided on 5G as the technology of choice for C-V2X. 3GPP's technical specification groups (TSGs) provide relevant specifications and technologies for V2X services, though navigating through the numerous documents can be complex. Releases 14 and 15 introduced V2X enhancements in 4G, while 5G's Rel-16 extended architectural aspects and service-oriented functionalities for advanced V2X services. Rel-16 and Rel-17 focus on NR sidelink communication improvements, resource allocation, power efficiency, and new use-case scenarios. The evolution of C-V2X spans V2V standards, essential safety services, stable LTE-V2X in 4G, and advanced C-V2X services in 5G NR-V2X, delivering lower latency, ultra-reliability, and higher throughput. The depicted phases guide researchers in developing V2X solution components. In short, the authors examined the 3GPP's support for V2X services in 4G, NSA-based 5G, and SA-based 5G, as well as the communication needs, use cases, significant problems, and potential solutions. Additional summarized information is provided in Fig. 3.

The requirements set by 3GPP ensure that the communication system can effectively handle the demands of various applications. By addressing the performance requirements in Table 2, the communication system can effectively support advanced V2X scenarios for various use case groups, ranging from safety applications to traffic management, efficient navigation, and enhanced driver assistance.

Real-world testing on the C-V2X network revealed the significance of specific configurations for achieving effective autonomous driving communication. In a study by [10], field trials conducted across Europe

Fig. 2. C-V2X communications.

Fig. 3. 3GPP Roadmap towards full 5G NR C-V2X.

Table 2
Performance Requirements to Support Advanced V2X Scenarios for Use Case Groups.

Group	End-to-end la-tency (ms)	Payload (Bytes)	Message/ Sec	Data rate (Mbps)	Min range (m)	Reliability (%)
Vehicle platooning	10–25	50–6500	2–50	50–65	80–350	90–99.99
Remote driving	5	–	–	UL:25 DL:1	–	99.999
Extended sensors	10–100	1600	10	10–90	50–1000	90–99.999
Advanced driving	3–10	2000–12,000	10–100	30–53	360–700	99.999

and China examined the performance of 5G/LTE-V2X networks under different conditions, including variations in antenna height, driving speeds, and terrain. Vehicles equipped with onboard units were connected to a 5G or LTE infrastructure, making it possible to measure some factors such as latency, data throughput, packet loss, and connectivity impact. Packet loss rates were approximately 10%, which shows promise but also emphasizes the importance of optimal network configuration to meet the stringent requirements of autonomous driving.

Moreover, in [11], the authors proposed a resource allocation method that addresses high-reliability constraints for multicasting automotive messages in 5G NR C-V2X networks. Based on a successive convex approximation method, the algorithm enhanced network performance under high computational demands. Tests showed improvements in reliability and latency, indicating the potential of resource management techniques to support autonomous driving requirements effectively.

Adopting C-V2X with 5G NR technology is critical to achieve full automation. Testing and standardization progress will be essential to develop the low-latency, high-reliability network required to support fully autonomous vehicles in the real world. This creates the basis to achieve the connectivity needed to exchange information between all the components of a cooperative infrastructure.

2.2. Intelligent transport systems (ITS)

ITS transform transportation by combining cutting-edge technology, communication networks, and information processing to improve productivity, security, and sustainability. These systems comprise various components that work in unison to streamline traffic networks and offer authorities and users real-time information [12]. Traffic management systems use sensors, cameras, and data analytics to monitor and control traffic flow. Techniques include adaptive traffic signal control, incident detection and management, and congestion pricing.

Traveler information systems offer real-time updates on traffic conditions, travel times, detour options, and public transportation schedules. To achieve a cooperative approach, ITS can send a set of possible messages across the network, categorized into several services. V2I Safety messages include curve speed advice, stop sign gap assistance, and red-light violation warnings. V2P safety messages, meanwhile, help secure signalized crosswalks by notifying approaching vehicles. V2V safety services include alerts about hazardous passing situations, forward collision warnings, blind spot detection, and emergency electronic brake lights. The Environment category prioritizes eco-friendly driving by synchronizing speeds to maximize fuel efficiency, allowing cooperative adaptive cruise control, and optimizing traffic signal timing. Lastly, road weather services provide real-time data and alerts to help vehicles navigate hazardous conditions safely. A framework for ITS developed by the European Telecommunications Standardization Institute (ETSI) is shown in Fig. 4. This framework offers a modular communication system that can be customized for various traffic control applications and is compatible with different communication technologies [13]. Three major players in an ITS scenario are vehicles, roadside infrastructure, and a centralized management system. Each represents a unique subsystem. In the figure’s lower blocks, the OSI protocol stack divides communication responsibilities across layers:

- Access (Layers 1 and 2) handles physical data transmission.
- Networking and Transport (Layers 3 and 4) manage data routing and delivery. The “Applications” component contains ITS apps that connect using these services, working together to provide comprehensive ITS solutions.

The ITS system employs a layered design for efficient communication. The access layer uses protocols like WIMAX and General Packet Radio Service (GPRS) to manage physical data transmission over wireless and wired mediums [15]. It supports both internal device commu-

Fig. 4. ETSI ITS Communication Architecture [14].

nication and external connectivity to other stations. The network and transport layers use protocols like IPv6 to ensure effective data delivery, handle congestion, and maintain message reliability. The facilities layer includes functions designed for ITS applications, keeping data storage and communication addressing with message processing protocols, while allowing devices to download additional software modules for enhanced functionality. This information is essential to maintaining a cooperative system and is distributed through smartphone applications, moving message signs, and in-car navigation systems. In [16], a study investigated a system to collect, deliver, and display road weather data to improve driving under adverse weather conditions and enhance traffic safety. The study involved a 260km route, six trucks equipped to collect data, and real-time weather forecasts. The ITS technology enhances system efficiency and reliability when applied to public transportation systems. Real-time tracking, automatic fare collection, and transit signal priority improve customer experience. Similarly, ITS enables the quick deployment of electronic toll collection, eliminating the need for physical toll booths and easing traffic congestion. This is achieved through RFID and ITS messaging. Incident management systems improve the detection and handling of road incidents, enabling quicker coordination among emergency services, traffic authorities, and road users. In Smart Cities, ITS facilitates seamless connectivity for autonomous vehicles, public transportation, and infrastructure, transforming vehicles into real-time information sources for traffic and resource management [17]. Technologies like autonomous driving, advanced driver-assistance systems (Advanced driver-assistance system (ADAS)), V2X, V2V, and V2I communication enable cars to interact with one another and the surrounding infrastructure [18]. In Europe, ITS plays a critical role in reducing pollution and congestion while enhancing safety. ICT technologies encourage secure, effective, and environmentally friendly transportation across all modes. The EC collaborates with Member States, businesses, and governmental agencies to overcome deployment challenges and ensure coherent implementation. Studies like [19] discuss ITS contributions to energy conservation and emission reduction, identifying how optimal vehicle specifications and government-backed energy-saving policies can further these efforts, particularly in Smart Cities. Rapid advances in ITS are expected in the coming years, driven by cooperative ITS (Cooperative-Intelligent Transport Systems (C-ITS)) and automation, which enable efficient data exchange and communication between vehicles, infrastructure, and users. The C-ITS system helps create a

cleaner, safer, and more efficient transportation system by reducing environmental impact, maximizing infrastructure use, and improving safety. The EC aims to leverage ITS systems to enhance transportation network management and optimize passenger and business operations [20]. Portugal’s adoption of ITS Law No. 32/2013, which recognizes ITS in road transport, reflects this trend, aligning with Directive No. 2010/40/EU [21]. The costs associated with traffic congestion are significant, estimated at €100 billion in 2012 [22], but implementing C-ITS services brings benefits that outweigh these costs [23]. C-ITS can employ both direct short-range connections (V2V) and cellular networks (3G, 4G, 5G), as shown in Fig. 5, to allow effective communication across multiple levels of automation. Studies like [24] demonstrate ITS applications in pedestrian-to-vehicle (P2V) communication, proposing a framework where smartphones and vehicular communication systems enhance pedestrian safety. Similarly, study [25] focuses on collision prevention between cars and bicycles using low-cost C-ITS stations. Such initiatives demonstrate the critical role of C-ITS in improving road safety and efficiency. ITS services rely on accessible radio communication technologies. Dedicated Short Range Communications (DSRC) and V2X operate in designated frequency bands (e.g., 700 MHz and 5.9 GHz) for critical applications like automated driving. Table 3 summarizes the characteristics of these technologies by service type. For example, electronic toll collection uses DSRC for bidirectional data over short distances, while V2X supports vehicle and road safety applications at longer ranges.

Safety is a priority in these services. Secure communication is critical for DSRC and cellular-based C-V2X technology, especially for ADAS and automated driving. However, achieving interoperability between ITS-G5 and C-V2X standards involves technical and regulatory challenges, particularly spectrum allocation and backward compatibility across regions [26]. Ensuring seamless integration of these standards remains a primary focus for organizations like ETSI and 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) [27]. In the coming years, integrating ITS with advanced technologies like 5G and networked remote units (New Radio Unlicensed (NR-U)) will expand the system’s range, allowing for extensive infrastructure communication beyond the current OSI model. These advancements enhance interoperability and address security, latency, and scalability challenges.

2.2.1. Standards and interoperability: ITS-G5, DSRC, and C-V2X

The terms DSRC and ITS-G5 are often used interchangeably to refer to the same communication technology, with DSRC more commonly used in North America and ITS-G5 in Europe [28]. Both technologies play essential roles in ITS, enabling communication between vehicles (V2V) and infrastructure (V2I), to support cooperative and safer

Fig. 5. ETSI C-ITS Communications.

Table 3
Characteristics of radio technologies per ITS service.

Service types	Radio communication technologies	Information	Radio Coverage	Message Latency
ETC	DSRC	Bi-directional data	Small (~100 m)	Low (<100 ms)
Vehicle and Road Safety	700 MHz or 5.9 GHz band V2X	Bi-directional data, Data Broadcasting	Medium (~1000 m)	Low (<100 ms)
Traffic Information Service	TPEG	Data Broadcasting	Wide (~100 km)	Medium (~1 s)
Autonomous Driving	V2X	Bi-directional data, Data Broadcasting	Medium (~1000 m)	Low (<5 ms)

transportation systems. Essential standards that govern ITS-G5 or DSRC communication include ETSI EN 302 663 and IEEE 802.11p for vehicular communication protocols, EN 302 571 for security services, and EN 302 637, which outlines certificate management and security components [29–31].

Despite regional nomenclature variations, the fundamental concepts and objectives of V2V and V2I communication are consistent, ensuring interoperability across platforms for secure and efficient transportation.

A comparative study of vehicular communication systems on unlicensed versus licensed DSRC bands showed that performance was comparable in the 2.4–2.5 GHz unlicensed frequency range, although there was a 30% drop in packet delivery rate on the 5.725–5.875 GHz unlicensed band [27]. This highlights the potential interference challenges on unlicensed frequencies, underscoring the need for further research into the performance and coexistence of vehicular systems on non-regulated frequencies (NR-U).

Beyond DSRC and ITS-G5, C-V2X is a communication technology that supports V2N and V2V modes through 3GPP standards, namely LTE-V2X and 5G NR-V2X [32]. LTE-V2X leverages existing LTE networks, while 5G NR-V2X operates within 5G environments, providing advanced features such as low-latency communication and support for massive machine-type communication essential for highly dense traffic and automation.

While C-V2X and DSRC/IST-G5 differ in underlying communication methods and network dependencies, they both support crucial ITS applications. However, integrating these technologies remains an industry-wide challenge, with standardization bodies working toward effective interoperability across regions and systems.

To facilitate interoperability between ITS-G5 and C-V2X, several strategies have been proposed, including organizing communication using superframes with structured time slots, message headers, and reservation signals to manage occupied slots effectively [33]. These measures are designed to support compatibility between vehicles equipped with different communication technologies, thus enhancing overall system efficiency and road safety.

A real-world performance assessment compared DSRC/ITS-G5 and C-V2X under highway conditions. Results indicated that for short-range applications, C-V2X using PC5 typically achieved a higher range, while ITS-G5 provided lower latency in low-traffic density environments [26]. The study suggests that 4G C-V2X could potentially substitute some use cases that require long-range communication.

However, the advent of 5G C-V2X might further enhance range, latency, and scalability. Future research could explore the capabilities of 5G C-V2X in real-world deployments to evaluate its impact on communication reliability and efficiency, particularly within NR-U spectrum.

As discussed, precise and reliable localization is essential in autonomous driving. C-V2X technology enhances the vehicle's capacity

to navigate safely and effectively in dynamic environments. However, its effectiveness largely depends on the types of messages transmitted within the system, as messages with accurate localization are essential to achieve new levels of automation. Therefore, ensuring precise localization and encapsulating this data efficiently within these systems is fundamental.

All this showcases the importance of advanced localization techniques in autonomous driving, demanding a focused exploration of localization and the solutions available to support it. While GNSS provides a foundational layer for positioning, its limitations in urban and complex environments require additional methods. Therefore, advanced localization techniques, including relative positioning and hybrid GNSS-5G solutions, are increasingly essential to achieve the sub-meter accuracy demanded by autonomous vehicles.

The next chapter explores these localization methodologies, emphasizing the integration of GNSS with 5G technologies. It will highlight how different localisation methods can significantly enhance precision, establishing them as indispensable elements of the autonomous driving ecosystem.

3. Localization in V2X: leveraging 5G and gnss technologies

As autonomous and connected vehicle ecosystems develop, reliable network-based positioning has become an objective towards safe and efficient operations. Precise localization enables V2X systems to coordinate maneuvers and improve situational awareness. Given the limitations of standalone GNSS in complex urban environments, combining GNSS with 5G positioning offers an effective approach to achieve high precision and higher speeds in first position retrieval, required for autonomous systems.

This section discusses fundamental localization techniques, including GNSS, 5G-based positioning, and hybrid methods. When applied to ITS, these methods enable accuracy and efficiency to support different scenarios.

3.1. Positioning technologies

The 5G Core Network (CN) serves as the central component of the 5G network architecture and contains several interconnected elements designed to provide various services. One is the location-based functionalities for applications such as emergency services, asset monitoring, and location-based marketing [34]. In particular, the Location Management Function (LMF), introduced in Release 16 of the 3GPP standard [35], plays a crucial role in the 5G CN, explicitly enabling the location of mobile terminals and other connected devices. This addition enhances the network's capability to support advanced positioning applications essential for user safety and operational efficiency.

These services have dedicated regulations. [36] and [37] state minimum regulatory positioning target values. The maximum target is 50 m for 80% of UE for Horizontal positioning error, 5 m for 80% of UEs for vertical positioning error, and an end-to-end latency of 30 seconds. 5G evolves 4G's positioning architecture with adjustments for new components in the former's Core Network [38]. These leverage the geolocation capabilities of mobile devices to provide specific information and features based on the user's location [39]. With LTE, service providers can use the accuracy of the GPS built into mobile devices to offer various location-based services. However, 5G offers better characteristics when compared with LTE. 5G goes beyond its exclusive focus on location-based services, bringing substantial advancements to this domain.

The Next Generation Radio Access Network (NG-RAN) facilitates 5G positioning through a structured set of signaling protocols and interactions between network components, as illustrated in Fig. 6 and described in [40]. Within NG-RAN's functional framework, the gNB is divided into a Central Unit (CU) and a Distributed Unit (DU), which communicate via the F1 interface (1). To support accurate positioning,

Fig. 6. Existing protocols on data exchange between LMF, AMF, gNB(CU/DU) and UE.

the New Radio Positioning Protocol Annex (NRPPa) (2) enables data and positioning observations to be shared between the gNB and the LMF (3) [41]. Additionally, NG-RAN transmits essential radio setup data to the UE through the NR-Uu interface, part of the Radio Resource Control (RRC) layer (4,5).

For 5G positioning services between the UE and LMF, the LTE Positioning Protocol (LPP) has been extended to support both 4G and 5G advancements within a unified framework (6). This integration is essential for applications requiring precise and rapid positioning, such as V2V communication and precision industrial automation, where 5G's capabilities offer substantial advantages. Moreover, advanced antenna technologies, including beamforming and Massive MIMO, further enhance 5G network performance by improving efficiency, coverage, and accuracy in position calculations.

One way to add location management capabilities to the 5G CN is to use Location Services (LCS) built into it. LCS, mentioned on the state of the art [42], can locate devices using various location technologies such as Global Positioning Systems (GPS) and Cell ID, and it can be used for several use cases like vehicular localization, IoT and emergency scenarios, as reported in [43,44]. It will determine the final location provided by the network location algorithm and estimate the speed and accuracy of its location. Although some 4G components already perform some of these operations, 5G allows greater accuracy and a significantly higher number of operations without impacting the state of the network.

Another option is to use a positioning protocol such as the 5G Positioning Protocol, an extension of the LTE Positioning Protocol (LPP), designed to work with the 5G network architecture [37]. 5GPPP in [45] provides a standard positioning method that can be integrated into the 5G CN. It is also responsible for choosing the method to calculate the location based on the client's location (i.e., urban or non-urban),

required accuracy, and latency. This feature also makes it possible to combine information collected from different sources, i.e., a hybrid location service that can use the results of different algorithms and provide position estimates from all algorithms. One of the main advantages of the 5GPPP is its capacity to deliver exact location data, even when conventional positioning technologies, like GNSS, may not be accessible or efficient.

The 5G architecture, in service-based architecture (SBA) standardized by 3GPP, makes traditional network structures obsolete as they are divided into modular and interconnected services [34]. Each service embodies a specific business function to promote decentralized and agile network environments. These services communicate through distinct interfaces commonly used by APIs, service discovery, and registries concerning efficient communication within the SBA framework. Besides, a service mesh assists inter-service communication, offering functionality such as traffic management, security enforcement, and observability.

Rest protocol-based external connectivity towards SBI in the context of SBA has made the concept of SBA necessary for the use of prescribed communications protocols. To facilitate smooth component-to-component communication via the SBI, protocols such as the Non-Access-Stratum (NAS) and Next-Generation Application Protocol (NGAP) [46,47] are essential for controlling registration, connectivity, resource allocation, mobility, and context transmission within the 5G network.

The network architecture must be carefully considered to implement LMF functionality inside the 5G CN, with the SBI as the conduit linking all network components [42]. As seen in Fig. 7, LMF communicates with other network functions by sending HTTP POST requests using the Nlmf interface in a RESTful API manner. This integration emphasizes how

Fig. 7. 5G Architecture with Core Component, LMF and RAN.

crucial the SBI is to enabling harmonious and effective functioning in the context of 5G

Another critical 5G core function is the Access and Mobility Management Function (AMF), which uses the NAS protocol to record administration and connections, handle system identification and authorizations, and ultimately control network movement. To connect the LMF to the 5G core, an interface called Namf is required. This interface connects to the SBI and enables the usage of the function [34]. This interaction between the AMF and the LMF is needed to enable LBS for the users, and it will be responsible for managing the mobility and interacting with the LMF for managing the location information.

Although the LMF is optional, it can and should be implemented in a 5G system to enhance location management capabilities. While the AMF is responsible for some location functionality, the LMF brings added value. It will allow additional flexibility regarding algorithms, permitting customization and optimization in specific use cases. It also increases accuracy by working with the AMF and integrating various location data sources, such as GPS and Wi-Fi. It allows a broader range of services, such as geographic data analysis, that require higher resources. While the AMF is essential, the LMF is desirable, especially when moving forward with autonomous cars, where it can become an indispensable asset.

Fig. 8. Diagram supporting the communication between all positioning components (adapted from [48]).

An external or internal service can request the location of a UE within the 5G core. Fig. 8 illustrates the sequence of interactions between components to retrieve the UE's location. The process begins with a positioning request to the AMF, identifying the UE, and initiating the required procedures to retrieve positioning data from the RAN. The AMF manages this identification and handling process (steps 3 and 4).

After identification, the LMF retrieves relevant data from the RAN to determine the appropriate positioning algorithm [35]. The LMF then transmits the UE's positioning capabilities, provides assistance data, and requests location information from the UE itself (step 5). Once the initial communication is established, the LMF may request additional data. If positioning capabilities have already been retrieved from the AMF, these transfer steps may be omitted, streamlining the process.

When data from one or more gNBs is received, the LMF runs the selected algorithm to calculate the UE's position. Subsequently, the LMF issues a Determine Location Response service request to the AMF, which includes the computed position or any approximate location data available (step 6). This process, also examined in [48], underscores the interactions and algorithms necessary for efficient and accurate UE positioning within the 5G core.

One important note is that at this moment, the open-source 5G CN implementations, like OpenAirInterface², Open5GS³ and Free5GC⁴, still do not have support for the LMF function. Being novel and mentioned in Release 17 of 3GPP [42], there is still ongoing integration work for deploying such a function on the 5G core and improving the QoS.

In [49], the author exposes the benefits of 5G positioning for Vehicular Safety Applications. The development of V2X technology in 5G enables interaction between cars and a variety of components on the road, including roadside infrastructure and units, people and networks. It makes it possible to have high-speed and dependable low-latency connections. The combination of Ultra-Reliable and Low Latency Communications (URLLC) and very accurate localization makes 5G the first technology to satisfy the demanding needs of applications for road safety. The authors' study outlines a common understanding across value chain participants about using radio positioning and sensing for road safety inside the 5G ecosystem. They look at the essential architectural features and technological advancements that make it possible to meet the stringent localization and communication requirements. Radar sensors detect other cars or obstacles in several road safety cases, including cooperative movements and interactive virtual road users. As a result, radar performance, including range accuracy and Doppler resolution, becomes essential for guaranteeing safety. Bistatic radar sensing can be used by employing improved resolution and multipath measurements from down-link positioning reference signals or uplink sounding reference signals. This method predicts the locations of things that reflect wireless signals and passive or disconnected objects. Improving environmental awareness not only helps to satisfy the criteria of applications for vehicle safety but also improves the performance of UE locations. The authors concluded that given the complexity of the ITS ecosystem and services, whether these technological advancements will be adopted in the car industry is still questionable. One of the future technologies that can deliver road sensing data on board is the V2X connection. Therefore, it is essential to work on and test the adoption of these systems.

Given the importance of localization for in-vehicle communication and cooperation, how it can be retrieved under the 5G systems will be significant, and the LMF has that role. However, how can the LMF process information to provide the localization of a UE? The following section will study the 5G position techniques included in the LMF.

3.1.1. LMF positioning mechanisms

The LMF function will permit adding different kinds of position algorithms. As mentioned in [50], there are four types of positioning techniques:

- *Cell-Identity-Based Localization Techniques*: These techniques find ways to locate a mobile device or user's location using the information supplied by cellular networks about their cell identification. It is a more straightforward method when compared with others.
- *Angle-Based Localization Techniques*: These methods estimate a mobile device's or user's location based on the angle of wireless signals. These techniques leverage the spatial information provided by the angles at which signals propagate between the device and the surrounding infrastructure.
- *Range-Based Localization Techniques*: refer to techniques for determining the position of a mobile device or user using information about the distance or range between the device and a collection of anchors or references. These methods use measurements of the wireless signal propagation characteristics to calculate the separation between the device and the reference sites.
- *Fingerprinting-Based Localization Techniques*: refer to techniques for determining a mobile device's or user's position based on a comparison between received and a database of signal fingerprints linked to known places. These methods build a fingerprint or signature for each place using the patterns and properties of wireless signals.

Techniques from these types of positioning appear in different types of algorithms, such as Enhanced Cell ID (E-CellID), Round Trip Time (RTT), Time of Arrival (ToA), Time Difference of Arrival (TDOA), Angle of Arrival (AoA) and Angle of Departure (AoD).

E-CellID, part of the Cell-Identity-Based Localization Techniques, increases mobile device tracking and location accuracy. It is an improved variant of the conventional Cell ID approach, which locates mobile devices by determining the serving cell tower. More data is acquired from the network infrastructure to improve the precision of position determination in the E-CellID system. This data may include signal intensities, time delays, and information from nearby cell towers. Compared to the traditional Cell ID, the E-CellID system can offer a more accurate estimate of the device's location by considering these parameters. In urban settings with closely placed cell towers, where traditional Cell ID methods are less reliable owing to signal overlap and multipath interference, E-CellID technology is beneficial. These restrictions may be circumvented, and E-CellID can deliver more accurate location information by adding extra data. Some work was done in this area on [51], which concluded that the NRPos framework offers better location accuracy than current methods like OTDOA and E-CellID. The suggested framework is a potential option for geolocation in NR systems since it can be deployed like ECID and provides superior accuracy to OTDOA. In [52], a single base station was used in the study to evaluate the E-CID positioning approach with error reduction in real-world 5G scenarios. The findings demonstrated that the suggested approach may produce precise indoor positioning suited for business applications.

In 5G, one of the location techniques is called ToA, and it discovers the locating of a UE by comparing the times at which a signal is transmitted from the UE to various BS and calculating the distance to each BS based on the variations in the times at which the signal arrives at each BS, like in [50]. Another technique is the TDOA which is a method for determining a signal's location based on the variations in the signal's arrival timings at various receiving sites. It is frequently used in wireless communication systems, such as radar systems and cellular networks, to pinpoint the location of a transmitter or target. There are differences between the two algorithms, like ToA requires a single receiving point equipped with a synchronized clock, and TDOA requires three or more receiving points. In ToA, the distance between the source and the receiving point is calculated by multiplying the signal's propagation

² <https://openairinterface.org/>.

³ <https://open5gs.org/>.

⁴ <https://free5gc.org/>.

speed by the measured arrival time.

Furthermore, the TDOA is often used with trilateration or multilateration (hyperbolic positioning) techniques to pinpoint the location of the signal source. [53] developed simulations, revealing that while comparing different methods, there were considerable disparities in the precision and availability of the acquired location estimations. The network topology and the location of the target node affect how well the algorithms function.

Another method is the AoD, one of the techniques used in radio positioning devices to locate a transmitter. The determination of AoD is made possible in 5G using numerous antenna devices for signal transmission and reception. With Millimeter Wave (mmWave) frequencies (which are used in 5G for high-speed data transfer, but have a smaller range than lesser frequency bands), this is especially helpful [50]. The AoA is a technique used to estimate the direction or angle from which a signal arrives at a receiving point. There are various methods to determine the AoA, depending on the specific implementation and system requirements. For example, beamforming techniques, such as phased array antennas spaced apart, can be used to estimate the AoA, and triangulation where the AoA can be estimated using the signal's arrival angles at multiple receiving points.

Table 4 summarizes the number of base stations required for each positioning methodology, the requirements, and the suitability for the frequency range in the context of 5G networks. More frequency information can be found on [54]. In [55], the authors propose a theoretical localization constraint for a lens-MIMO system utilized in cooperative V2V communication at a street intersection is introduced in this paper. The outcomes of the lens-MIMO system are contrasted with those of the traditional uniform linear array (ULA). It explores the estimate of the AoA with a condensed technique in addition to investigating the characteristics of the received signal in the lens-MIMO system. To do this, the authors put forth the R2SA AoA estimate method, which uses the ratio of the two most vital received signals at the antenna elements. This paper explores the theoretical bounds of localization for a lens-MIMO system in a cooperative V2V communication scenario at a street intersection. The outcomes from the lens-MIMO system and the traditional ULA are contrasted. It examined the lens-MIMO system's attributes of the received signal and the estimate of the AoA using a streamlined methodology. The authors proposed the R2SA AoA estimate method, which uses the ratio between the two most vital signals at the antenna elements.

RTT can play a role in determining the location of a mobile device. It is crucial to remember that RTT could not be the primary positioning technique in 5G networks. It needs to be integrated into other techniques. In [56], the authors propose to enhance the performance of 5G

Table 4
Comparison of the Methodology for Positioning in 5G

Methodology	Requirements	Suitability	Number of Base Station
ToA	Comparison of signal transmission times to calculate distance	FR1 and FR2	2 or more
TDoA	Variation in signal arrival times at multiple receiving points	FR1 and FR2	3 or more
AoD	Estimation of the direction or angle from which a signal arrives	FR2 (especially with mmWave)	2 or more
AoA	Estimation of the direction or angle from which a signal arrives	FR1 and FR2	2 or more
e-CID	Information about cell identification provided by cellular networks	FR1 and FR2	1
RTT	Calculation of time taken for a signal to travel to a reference point and back	FR1 and FR2	2 or more

location in complicated situations with few visible base stations. The paper explores the relationship between RTT and AoD positioning techniques in 5G networks. It analyzes the impact of base station geometry distribution on positioning accuracy and reliability. The theoretical simulation experiments are conducted in excellent and complex environments to compare the results before and after incorporating AoD measurements. The findings reveal that adding AoD measurements significantly enhances positioning accuracy, with horizontal accuracy improving by over 25% and vertical accuracy by over 65%. Furthermore, including AOD measurements improves positioning reliability and addresses the challenge of RTT measurements alone not being able to position accurately in scenarios with fewer than three base stations. However, this opens space for future research to optimize these algorithms for complex scenarios, like autonomous systems in V2V communications.

There are various recent works exploring different types of position algorithms. In [57], a study was conducted on implementing an indoor positioning system using TDOA with existing 5G small cell networks. Their primary concern was finding solutions for the problems caused by indoor signal transmission. They created a channel model based on actual 5G measurements and utilized it to build a realistic simulation framework to address this. They were able to assess the efficiency of several algorithms using this approach. According to the study, some algorithms may successfully counteract the detrimental effects of non-line-of-sight (NLOS) propagation, resulting in positioning errors that, in some situations, are less than 3 m. They also learned that enhancing the Robust Weighted Least Squares (RWLS) technique, using power-delay profile-based (PDP) NLOS algorithms, and combining TDOA measurements with information from inertial measurement unit sensors or angular measurements from MIMO antenna systems are all means to increase accuracy. There was a following study [58] where the authors studied the performance of a TDOA indoor positioning solution in a real-world 5G network. The authors search for the optimized parameter settings determined with hyperparameter optimization, showing where these parameters' positioning error is a viable goal in some scenarios.

In [59], the author explores the performance limits relative to the positioning of vehicles in V2V with multiple antenna arrays. They used the AoA and TDOA measurements to estimate the vehicle's position in platooning scenarios. The results are met if, in the overtaking scenarios, the error does not exceed 22.46 m in longitudinal offset and 17.07m for the distance between vehicles.

There are also Machine Learning (ML) approaches, as in [60], where a proposed deep learning-based mmWave positioning method achieves unmatched accuracy levels in the presence of non-line-of-sight positions. The paper concludes that the proposed method significantly reduces the energy required for precise positioning in the presence of mmWave networks, enabling the design of more efficient and accurate positioning-enabled mobile devices. In [61], the challenges for the accurate position in natural environments are discussed, and a distance ratio position model based on the difference of received signal strength (DRSS) is proposed, significantly improving the accuracy of 5G positioning. For 80% of the samples, the method achieved a positioning error of 43.8 m using six base stations.

Table 5 analyzes the result of this extensive research.

A central function that could carry all these methods is a significant advance for all the 5G required use cases. Use cases like autonomous vessels leaving the dock and going to the deep sea, where all the positions from it and the other vessels are being calculated with the view of helping the processing of the autonomous algorithms. Another use case can be for autonomous driving [43], where the position is essential, keeping the whole environment safe and keeping track of your actions.

In conclusion, the LMF can be integrated into the 5G CN using a variety of location determination techniques, positioning protocols, and indoor positioning systems, which can enhance the precision and dependability of the LMF. It is crucial for handling user and device

Table 5
Comparison of the positioning techniques in 5G networks.

Literature	Algorithm	Input Data Type	Simulation Type	Environment	Field Type	Error
[51]	NRPos-Algorithm	E-CID	simulated	outdoor	X	<10m
[52]	Cumulative Distribution Function	E-CID, ToA, AoA	realistic	indoor	Controlled test	<3m
[55]	AoA estimation algorithm	AoA	simulated	outdoor (vehicle)	X	<1m
[56]	Multi-RTT positioning model	RTT, AoD	simulated	outdoor	X	<2m
[57]	Robust Weighted Least Squares +RANSAC and IDD combined	TDoA	realistic	indoor	Controlled test	<3m
[59]	Deriving Cramer–Rao bound	AoA, TDoA	realistic	outdoor (vehicle)	Controlled test	<1m
[60]	BFF positioning method, ML	AoA	simulated	outdoor	X	<15m
[61]	Levenberg-Marquardt based maximum a posteriori algorithm	DRSS	realistic	outdoor	Field test	<45m

location data within the network and offers exact location-based services necessary for emergency services and other uses.

Other technologies will be used to obtain the UE's precise position besides the 5G position techniques, with GNSS being one of them. The following section will describe that technology and its methods in more detail.

3.2. GNSS for vehicular positioning

A robust infrastructure is essential to fully realize the potential of the automotive sector and leverage the benefits of autonomous driving. Such an infrastructure must support reliable communications and provide accurate position information for vehicles, which function as User Equipments (UE) within the network, utilizing both 5G and GNSS methods. Through GPS and GNSS technologies, it is possible to determine the precise location of a person, object, or vehicle nearly anywhere on Earth. These systems play a vital role in applications like mapping, fleet monitoring, mobile device geolocation, vehicle navigation, and scientific research.

GPS was the first global positioning system developed and maintained by the United States government [62]. Initially developed for military use only, GPS was made available for civilian use. However, it is still used extensively by the armed forces of many countries for navigation, positioning, and guidance of troops, vehicles, and munitions. GPS consists of a constellation of satellites in orbit around the Earth, which transmit radio signals containing information about their location and precise time [63]. GPS receivers, found in devices such as smartphones and vehicle navigation systems, receive these signals and use the information to calculate the receiver's position based on the arrival time of signals from multiple satellites.

GNSS is a broader term encompassing the United States GPS and other global positioning systems developed by different countries. Examples of other GNSS systems include Russia's GLONASS, the European Union's Galileo, and China's BeiDou. These systems work similarly to GPS, using a constellation of satellites and receivers to calculate the user's position.

Each GNSS satellite transmits a data set called an almanac, which contains precise orbital information and timing parameters. GNSS receivers need this data to calculate the user's position accurately. However, the almanac is a large data file the receivers must download [64]. Fortunately, many modern devices can receive automatic almanac updates, making the process easier for users. In addition, GNSS systems allow the sending of real-time corrections, known as Real-Time Kinematic (RTK), to improve positioning accuracy further. It is essential in applications that require high accuracy, such as land surveying, precision agriculture, and infrastructure construction.

GNSS systems offer positioning accuracy ranging from a few meters to centimeters, depending on the type of application and the capabilities available on the receiver used. In addition to position determination, these systems can provide information such as velocity, direction, and altitude. It is important to note that for these systems to obtain good

GNSS signal reception, it is necessary to have a clear view of the sky without obstructions such as tall buildings or dense tree cover [65]. The signal can be blocked or attenuated in urban or enclosed environments, causing the user's position calculation faults.

In summary, GNSS systems are technologies that allow precise determination of the geographic position anywhere in the world based on signals transmitted by satellites. These systems have wide application and positively impact many areas of our society, allowing services that operate based on accurate and reliable location information. GNSS systems have revolutionized many areas, such as transportation, logistics, and more. The ability to obtain precise location information anywhere in the world has paved the way for a wide range of location-based applications and services, becoming essential in our daily lives.

3.2.1. GNSS techniques for vehicular localization

The Time to First Fix (TTFF) is the duration required for a GNSS device to receive signals from a sufficient number of satellites (typically four or more) to calculate its position accurately [66]. Before a GNSS receiver can determine its location, it must gather three essential data types:

- Signals from multiple satellites
- Almanac data: contains less accurate orbital information than ephemeris and is used to speed up time to first fix by 15 seconds (compared to not having almanac stored) - this data is valid for 90 days and takes 12.5 minutes to download.
- Ephemeris data: contains information on week number, satellite accuracy, and health, age of data, satellite clock correction coefficients, orbital parameters - this data is valid for two hours before and two hours after the time of ephemeris time-of-emission (TOE) and takes 30 seconds to download.

The GNSS requires a minimum of four satellite observations and all the necessary data to resolve the existing errors to obtain high accuracy correctly. This is because GNSS assumes an 'earth-centered, earth fixed, x-y-z 3D cartesian coordinate system'. Any location in this 3D space requires no more than three components to be completely identified. So, three satellites could be used to determine three position dimensions with a 'perfect' receiver clock. However, since this is not true for most receivers, because the receiver's local time differs from the satellite's (GPS satellites, for example, use atomic clocks kept in sync via control signals from the ground to an accuracy of plus or minus three nanoseconds). As an example, if the receiver's local time is out of sync with the satellite's time by just 1 millisecond, this translates to a distance error of about 300 kms. Thus, a fourth satellite is needed to eliminate the equation's receiver time variable.

Nevertheless, it is assumed to be an almost perfect error-free system, where the only error that must be fixed is the satellite's orbit coordinates. Each satellite observation includes a single equation connecting the geometric range (distance) from the receiver to the satellite, the signal travel time, and the receiver's clock delay. Each satellite

observation supplies one equation, and four unknowns will be solved (x, y, z , and receiver time t_r). In geometry, the range between two points requires a nonlinear square root procedure, making it difficult to solve the unknowns directly. Advanced algorithms and methods, such as least squares estimates or iterative procedures, are utilized to solve the nonlinear system of equations to acquire a precise solution. Resolving the equation to determine the positions of the satellites requires information that includes all relevant angles and reference points.

The necessary information is retrieved from the RINEX [67] (Receiver Independent Exchange Format) navigation files, frequently used in GNSS processing to give satellites exact orbit and time information, which is critical for adequately resolving unknowns.

Assuming an error-free system is not valid in a natural environment since the signal must travel from space to the Earth’s surface, it must go through the ionospheric and tropospheric layers of the atmosphere, and thus, those errors must be accounted for. All the errors needed to accurately calculate the position using the GNSS are shown in Table 6.

Fig. 9 supports a better understanding of all the errors on the table. The errors can be Satellite Clock Errors (where the satellite’s atomic clocks may not be entirely accurate), Orbital Errors (associated with inaccuracies in the reported location of the satellite), Ionospheric Delay (when the satellite signal as it passes through the ionosphere), Tropospheric Delay (when the signal passes through the Earth’s troposphere), Multipath Effect, Relativity Effect, and Receiver Noise.

The observation and navigation files provide all the raw data needed to process GNSS data and compute precise positions. It helps to develop many methods and techniques to solve or at least mitigate some parts of the errors in GNSS positioning systems, incorporating various techniques and methods to enhance accuracy, reliability, and availability. There are several methods to GNSS positioning:

- Multi-Costellation Support [68]: Modern receivers may track multiple satellite constellations simultaneously. This improves precision, availability, and dependability. It is instrumental in challenging environments like urban canyons, where signals may be hindered or attenuated.
- Precise Point Positioning (PPP) [69]: The very accurate GNSS computational technique provides a relatively exact location, velocity, and timing. It achieves similar precision levels to differential GNSS systems without a base station using a single GNSS receiver and exact satellite orbit and clock adjustments. It uses precise GNSS satellite location and clock data, often collected from sources like the IGS (International GNSS Service) to improve localisation. It can adjust for various GNSS inaccuracies, including ionospheric and tropospheric delays. Standard PPP, however, necessitates substantial computing complexity and ambiguity resolution, which prolongs the convergence time. It will take several minutes on a centimeter-level to have greater precision.

Table 6
GNSS Error Sources.

Source	Error	Symbol	Unit
Satellite	Clock offset	t_s	seconds
	Relativity offset	δ^{rel}	seconds
	Code bias	b_i^c	seconds
	Phase bias	B_i^p	seconds
	Antenna phase variations and offsets	ϵ_r^p	meters
	Phase wind-up	w_r^p	cycles
Atmosphere	Tropospheric delay	T_p^s	meters
	Ionospheric delay for index	$I_{r,i}^s$	meters
Receiver	Clock offset	t_r	seconds
	Code bias	$b_{r,i}$	seconds
	Phase bias	$B_{r,i}$	seconds
Others	True geometric range	ρ_r^s	meters
	Phase ambiguity	$N_{r,i}^p$	cycles

Fig. 9. Sources of GNSS pseudo-range measurement errors and Methods.

- Real-Time Kinematic (RTK) [70]: RTK uses a base station and rover to improve location data. It minimizes orbital and atmospheric delay errors. The rover’s location attains centimeter-level precision thanks to real-time base station adjustments. However, due to inaccuracies scaling with distance, precision is restricted to small ranges (less than 20 km). Due to the need for numerous base stations, RTK is unfeasible for autonomous cars and is better suited for constrained systems.
- PPP-RTK [71]: Combining the techniques of PPP and RTK, it is possible to have RTK adjustments for the rover’s ambiguity, orbit, clock, and atmospheric faults, reducing convergence time by clearing up the ambiguity. Without regard to distance, PPP-RTK maintains centimeter-level precision. Besides the legacy PPP-RTK, others like the “Trimble RTX” are recognized as improvements. Real-time communication and a network of reference stations are necessary.

Table 7 summarises the abovementioned methods, evidencing their pros and cons.

As a result, several research activities and projects are being undertaken to improve the accuracy and reaction time of the GNSS system.

Table 7
GNSS methods: pros and cons.

Method	Pros	Cons
Multi-Costellation Support	Increased Availability, Improved Accuracy, more Redundancy and Robustness, and Faster TTFF	Increased Complexity, Signal Interference, Increased processing power for data management and Signal Processing and Differing Standards
Precise Point Positioning (PPP)	Global Applicability, High Accuracy and Cost Efficiency	Long Convergence Times, Dependence on Precise Products, Limited Real-Time Applications, and Sensitivity to Errors
Real-Time Kinematic (RTK)	High Precision, Real-Time Solution and Fast Initialization	Need for a Base Station (typically less than 20–30 km), Data Link Requirement and Receiver cost
PPP-RTK	Global Applicability, High Accuracy and Real-Time Solution	Convergence Time, Dependence on Precise Corrections, Complex Data Processing and Communication Link Requirement

These efforts include strategies for re- solving ambiguity, different mistake correction services, and technique and application comparisons. Regarding location correction, there are two types of GNSS correction services: State Space Representation (SSR) and Observation State Representation (OSR). Both categories address the same issue, minimizing critical GNSS flaws such as orbits, biases, and clocks to enable high-precision GNSS performance. However, they use various approaches, delivery systems, and underlying technology.

Scalability of high positioning services is required to al- low world- wide mass market use. Due to specific constraints, legacy suppliers implementing OSR rectification data en- counter difficulty scaling up their services. On the other hand, SSR provides more current services that broadcast GNSS correction data, as seen in Fig. 10.

Users wanting centimeter-level precision while operat- ing a receiver within a 20-kilometer radius of the nearest ref- erence station might benefit significantly from OSR services [73]. On the one hand, their dependency on two-way com- munication with large bandwidth makes them less appropri- ate for mass market applications. On the other hand, SSR services can accomplish centimeter-level locations across broad areas with modest bandwidth needs, making them more suitable for mass market use. SSR services provide sev- eral advantages, including centimeter-level precision, world- wide coverage, one-way communi- cation, and minimal band- width utilization. Nonetheless, one signifi- cant disadvantage of SSR services is their reliance on proprietary formats. The primary differences between SSR and OSR [74] can be summarized as follows:

- **Mathematical Representation:** SSR represents the system using first- order state equations, whereas OSR directly ties the outputs to the system’s inputs and states.
- **Internal Dynamics:** SSR explicitly describes the sys- tem’s internal dynamics, capturing the change of state variables through time. OSR, on the other hand, does not explicitly simulate internal dynamics and concen- trates on observable outcomes.
- **Observability:** SSR allows for estimating the system’s internal states based on observable outputs, but OSR does not allow for the direct estimation of internal states.
- **Complexity:** SSR often results in a more complicated form due to the inclusion of state equations, whereas OSR provides a more straightforward representation directly linking outputs to inputs and states.

As illustrated in Fig. 10, both algorithms require a connection to the cellular network to transfer the correction data to the devices that need it to obtain a more accurate position.

Another essential method to position using GNSS is Precise Point

Positioning (PPP), in [75] expands the PPP strategy used in GNSS with an extended notion termed array-aided PPP (A-PPP). A-PPP improves the estimate of GNSS parameters such as location, altitude, time, and atmo- spheric delays using GNSS data from numerous antennas placed in a given geometry. The idea is intended to work with either standalone or combined multifrequency GNSS systems, both present and future. A-PPP is accomplished by resolving a brand-new multivariate integer least-squares problem with orthonormality constraints. The author shows that the integer matrix constraint is required to achieve accurate instantaneous attitude and position solutions. The orthonormality requirement must also be included in the integer ambiguity objective function to attain a high prob- ability of accurate integer estimation. A-PPP is used in var- ious situations, and its effectiveness is demon- strated using empirical GPS results. The A-PPP principle is generally applicable.

In the same way, [70] presents the development of an Australian PPP-RTK where the processing platform is an essential component of a multi-GNSS capable national po- sitioning infrastructure. By giving single-receiver users the capacity to execute integer ambiguity resolu- tion, the PPP- RTK idea expands the original PPP approach and dramati- cally speeds up convergence times. The PPP-RTK platform’s core ideas for the network and the user are elaborated in this article, and the GPS is used to show how well the platform performs. Additionally, the study offers a future prognosis for the platform’s performance once multi-GNSS constella- tions like BeiDou, Galileo, and QZSS (Quasi-Zenith Satel- lite System) are entirely operational.

[76] explores the PPP with Ambiguity Resolution (AR), a high-precision positioning technique that is becoming more prominent in geodetic and geophysical applications. The successful implementa- tion of PPP-AR [77] necessi- tates precise products like orbits, clocks, code, and phase biases. The paper examines the products generated by the Wuhan University Multi-GNSS Experiment (WUM) Anal- ysis Center (AC). It details the models and generation strategies of WUM rapid phase clock/bias and orbit-related products. These products are evaluated through comparison with products from other ACs and by testing the PPP- AR positioning precision using data from a specific period in 2022. Key findings indicate that the phase Observable- Specific Bias (OSB) fluctuates due to the clock day boundary discontinuities, but the peak-to-peak value remains within two ns. The GPS orbits show the best consistency with ESA products, while the orbits of other systems rank medium. The GLONASS clocks show slight inconsistencies due to the antenna thrust power, but no distortion is observed in the phase clocks of other GNSSs. The paper also reports an improvement in the intrinsic precision for Precise Orbit Determination (POD) with well-estimated phase products, which improved by 14%, 17%, and 24% for GPS, Gal- ileo and BeiDou-3, respectively.

Fig. 10. Correction services for high precision GNSS positioning(adapted from [72]).

With all the information obtained until now and the re- search done on [78], it is possible to affirm the differences between the PPP, PPP-AR, RTK, and PPP-RTK methods. The PPP is a high-accuracy positioning technique that leverages GNSS corrections to calculate precise positions for users with single receivers. This method can achieve centimeter- level accuracy, making it highly valuable for various applications. However, one drawback of PPP is its relatively long convergence times, typically ranging from minutes to tens of minutes. The PPP-AR was developed to address the issue of slow convergence in the PPP. It aims to expedite the position estimation process by resolving ambiguities in the carrier phase measurements. By resolving these ambiguities, PPP- AR significantly reduces the time required to achieve high- accuracy positioning results.

On the other hand, RTK is another high-precision positioning technique that employs a fixed base station and a mobile receiver. Finally, the PPP-RTK, a technique that combines the strengths of both PPP and RTK, offers real-time corrections while maintaining faster convergence times. The key to PPP-RTK's enhanced performance lies in broadcasting regional or local-area ionospheric and tropospheric corrections, which facilitate real-time high-precision positioning with improved efficiency. The main difference between PPP-RTK and RTK lies in their error correction message transmission. In RTK, all the errors are sent in a single heavy message, which includes errors that may require updating at different intervals. For example, some errors, such as orbits, only need to be sent every 15 minutes, while others, such as clock errors, require updates every 30 seconds. In RTK, all errors are bundled together and sent in a single message every 30 seconds, regulated by the most critical error. This results in a heavy data load.

In contrast, PPP and PPP-RTK adopt different approaches. They send each correction separately, each with its time interval. This method helps to reduce network saturation since the errors are sent only when necessary, based on their specific update requirements. By transmitting corrections individually at different intervals, PPP and PPP-RTK optimize the use of network resources, leading to a more efficient and less burdensome data transmission process.

In summary, PPP achieves centimeter-level accuracy but with longer convergence times, while PPP-AR reduces convergence times by resolving carrier phase ambiguities. RTK delivers real-time centimeter-level accuracy using a fixed base station and a mobile receiver. Lastly, PPP-RTK combines real-time corrections with faster convergence times, enabled by broadcasting regional or local-area ionospheric and tropospheric corrections. Each method offers distinct advantages, catering to diverse user requirements in high- precision positioning and navigation.

Another essential approach is using the Kalman Filter for error correction in GNSS positioning [79]. The filter uses a series of measurements observed over time and produces estimates of unknown variables by minimizing the mean of the squared error. In the context of GNSS, these variables include an object's position, velocity, and acceleration.

In general, the successful resolution of ambiguities is also influenced by other factors, such as the quality of the GNSS receiver, the number and geometry of the observed satellites, and the user's environment (for instance, multipath can significantly complicate ambiguity resolution).

3.2.2. GNSS techniques: single and double differences

As mentioned before, in GNSS, using single and double- difference techniques is instrumental in refining the accuracy of satellite-based positioning. The single-difference technique (SDT) is one in which the GNSS measurements from two different receivers of the same satellite are compared. This approach primarily targets mitigating shared errors between the receivers, such as inaccuracies in satellite clocks and atmospheric delays, including ionospheric and tropospheric variations. This method is prevalent in Differential GNSS (DGNSS) systems, including Real-Time Kinematic (RTK) positioning. Although SDT significantly improves positioning accuracy, it does not eliminate errors

intrinsic to the receivers, such as those caused by multipath effects or inherent receiver noise [80].

The main difference between SDT and the double- difference technique (DDT) is error mitigation. DDT is more effective than SDT in reducing a more comprehensive range of errors, including those associated with the receiver's clock. When implemented, DDT is generally more complex than SDT. The DDT requires a more stable and continuous connection from both receivers to identical satellites for data requirements. Finally, the accuracy of DDT generally provides higher accuracy than SDT, but at the cost of increased complexity and data requirements [81]. The DDT builds upon the concept of an SDT. It involves different measurements from two satellites observed by two separate receivers. This process, essentially a difference of differences, is more adept at reducing a more comprehensive array of errors. It efficiently mitigates errors common to the satellite signals and those associated with the receiver's clock, thus providing a more refined accuracy level. The application of DDT is particularly crucial in high-precision tasks like geodetic surveying, where the utmost accuracy is imperative. However, this method demands both receivers' stable and continuous observation of identical satellites, making it more complex and data-intensive. Interruptions in the signal can significantly complicate the DDT process. The distinction between these two techniques lies in their approach to error correction and complexity. SDT reduces satellite clock errors, whereas DDT eliminates satellite and receiver clock errors, offering higher precision. The paper's exploration of multi-GNSS solutions includes these differential techniques to optimize attitude determination accuracy, underscoring the importance of robust and precise navigation solutions for vehicles in various environmental conditions. The choice between DS or DDT in GNSS applications depends on the necessary balance between accuracy, complexity, and data availability. With its more straightforward implementation and lower data requirements, SDT is sufficient for many standard GNSS applications. In contrast, despite its complexity and stringent data needs, DDT is the preferred approach in scenarios where accuracy is non-negotiable.

In the realm of GNSS, accuracy and precision are paramount. In table 8, the SDT and DDT techniques are two standard methods employed to enhance the accuracy of position measurements. Each method has its unique approach and implications for GNSS data processing. Table 8 provides a comparative overview of these two methods, highlighting their definitions, advantages, and limitations. This comparison is instrumental for professionals and researchers in choosing the appropriate technique based on their specific accuracy requirements and application contexts.

In the context of autonomous vehicle real-time applications, [82] delves into enhancing attitude determination accuracy in dynamic environments for vehicle navigation by using multiple GNSS constellations (GPS, BDS, GLONASS, Galileo). A vital aspect of this study involves understanding the differences between SDT and DDT techniques in GNSS data processing. In the context of this paper, SDT could be used to compare data from the vehicle-mounted receivers with a reference receiver, thereby enhancing the accuracy of the attitude determination by reducing satellite-specific errors. On the other hand, the DDT takes this a step further by comparing the single differences between two

Table 8
Comparison of Single Difference and Double Difference in GNSS.

Aspect	Single Difference technique (SDT)
Definition	Differencing measurements from two receivers to the same satellite.
Pros	Reduces common errors, Simpler to implement.
Cons	Limited error correction, Requires closely located receivers.
Aspect	Double Differences (DDT)
Definition	Difference of single differences between two satellites and two receivers.
Pros	Higher accuracy, Better for precise applications.
Cons	Complex, Requires stable satellite geometry.

satellites and two receivers, e.g., two vehicles, as a specific approach. This method could be more complex but offers higher precision as it eliminates both satellite and receiver clock errors. In the study, employing DDT would involve comparing signals from multiple satellites, such as the moving vehicle's receivers and a stationary reference. (ex. gNodeB). This approach is particularly beneficial in dynamic environments, as it significantly improves the reliability and accuracy of attitude determination by minimizing various error sources.

[83] introduces a DDT and dual-frequency model for exact positioning and attitude determination. This is particularly effective for observable GNSS signal resources, including satellites and transceivers, and this kind of approach could be significantly relevant for the Internet of Vehicles (IoV) applications, offering a low-cost, high-reliability, easily installed, and conveniently maintained solution. The integration of GNSS and pseudo-lite technology for enhanced positioning in urban areas and various other applications is discussed in the paper, which addresses technical challenges such as near-far signal strength, multipath errors, and time synchronization issues in GNSS networks. The results demonstrate high accuracy in positioning and attitude determination. For example, the measured horizontal direction error was less than 6 mm, and the vertical direction error was less than 15 mm. The system also effectively determined vehicle attitudes like head, pitch, and roll angles with minimal error.

In another case, [84] presents a comprehensive analysis of a GNSS spoofing detection technique based on double difference scattering. In this consideration, a differential carrier phase model involves two receivers observing identical satellites. This model calculates single carrier phase differences for each satellite in a standard view, considering factors such as geometric range, integer carrier phase ambiguity terms, receiver clock error, and differential noise. The algorithm proposed in this study uses the signal AoA. Under normal conditions, GNSS signals from different satellites arrive at the receiver from various directions.

In contrast, spoofed signals from a single source have a typical AoA. The algorithm differentiates between authentic and fake signals based on this principle. However, a third non-collinear antenna is required to resolve ambiguities inherent in a two-antenna system. In this case, the overall performance of the detection algorithm depends on the combination of pairwise detections. The overall probability of missed detection (PMD) is calculated based on the probability of detection for various combinations of DDT measurements. To increase detection robustness against noise, the paper suggests averaging fractional DDs over short intervals before deciding. This reduces noise variation and consequently affects the detection limit and the probabilities of missed detection and false alarms. Furthermore, using two baselines (i.e., adding a third antenna) allows simultaneous detection of spoofed signals on both baselines, increasing detection reliability.

3.2.3. Kalman filter for accurate positioning

The Kalman Filter [85] is a fundamental algorithm in control systems and signal processing, offering a robust solution for estimating the state of dynamic systems with different noisy measurements. Its iterative nature and computational efficiency are practical in precision-dependent, real-time applications like navigation systems.

The Kalman Filter enhances accuracy in GNSS positioning by addressing inherent challenges such as signal attenuation and satellite misalignment. This capability is especially relevant in PPP applications, where accuracy is critical and traditional GNSS methods may face limitations like signal degradation.

Thus, it can play a crucial role in increasing the positioning accuracy of the GNSS. This algorithm effectively addresses challenges inherent in GNSS, such as signal attenuation and satellite misalignment, especially in PPP method applications. By employing a recursive and linear approach, the Kalman Filter effectively integrates the dynamic characteristics of the model and observational data, thus enabling a more accurate estimation of the dynamic characteristics of a

mobile operator. This is particularly beneficial in real-time applications such as autonomous vehicles in obstructed spaces, where traditional navigation measurements are prone to contamination and inaccuracies [86,87].

One example is implementing Kalman Filtering in GNSS, and Inertial Navigation Systems (INS) integration further underscores its significance. An integrated navigation system can be achieved by using the difference in position and velocity as measured by GNSS and INS, providing more reliable positioning information. As applied in this context, the discrete Kalman filter algorithm estimates the state for the next moment based on the current system state, thus enhancing the overall navigation accuracy and reliability [88].

Furthermore, the Kalman Filter is proficient in fusing data from multiple sensors to improve positioning accuracy. Autonomous vehicles rely on various sensors, such as GPS, LiDAR, radar, and cameras, to perceive their environment. Each sensor, however, has its limitations and inaccuracies. This is done by weighting inputs based on their respective uncertainties, effectively filtering out noise and reducing the impact of single-sensor errors. This results in a more accurate understanding of the vehicle's condition, crucial for safe navigation and decision-making in complex and dynamic environments [89].

3.2.4. GNSS and 5G integration: LMF interactions

The LMF supports positioning techniques, including PPP, RTK, and PPP-RTK. Its primary function is to provide valuable assistance data to the UE to enhance the accuracy of its positioning capabilities [36].

With PPP, the LMF supplies essential assistance data to the UE. This data includes precise satellite orbits, clock corrections, code biases, and ephemeris and clock data if the UE has not acquired this information independently. The PPP technique achieves accurate single-station positioning by utilizing global networks of reference stations and atmospheric models. In the case of RTK, the LMF sends real-time corrections directly to the UE. These corrections are instrumental in improving positioning accuracy by eliminating errors common to the reference station and the UE. However, RTK requires the UE to be close to the reference station to achieve highly accurate positioning results. As done in PPP, the LMF interaction with PPP-RTK also provides real-time corrections, as in RTK, along with precise satellite orbit, clock data, and code biases obtained from reference stations. This combination enables PPP-RTK to achieve exceptional positioning accuracy even in regions beyond the reach of traditional RTK methods.

According to [90], in exploring advanced positioning techniques, the integration of PPP-RTK emerges as a promising approach. The LMF plays a crucial role in this integration by providing essential assistance data to the UE. In PPP, the LMF supplies data such as precise satellite orbits, clock corrections, and code biases, utilizing global reference networks and atmospheric models for accurate positioning. RTK, on the other hand, relies on the LMF for real-time corrections to reduce errors common between the UE and the reference station. However, RTK's effectiveness is limited by the proximity of the UE to the reference station. PPP-RTK overcomes this limitation by combining real-time corrections (as in RTK) with precise satellite data and code biases (as in PPP), enabling exceptional accuracy even in regions where traditional RTK is less effective.

In summary, the LMF plays a critical role in facilitating the exchange of assistance data between the UE and various positioning methods (PPP, RTK, and PPP-RTK), ultimately leading to more accurate positioning information for the UE. Depending on the positioning technique and the UE's requirements, the LMF can provide real-time or unsolicited periodic assistance data. Additionally, the UE can send GNSS measurements and other non-GNSS data to the LMF for location calculation or verification purposes. The 5G gNB links the 5G Vehicle Platform and the core network. Over this link, the vehicle transmits location or measurement data back to the LMF, which provides corrections and assistance data.

3.3. Hybrid positioning: GNSS and 5G integration

Hybrid positioning enables more precise and reliable location determination by combining multiple positioning methods, each compensating for the other's limitations. This approach leverages the strengths of different technologies, such as GNSS and cellular network-based positioning, to provide robust and adaptable location solutions.

Hybrid positioning typically integrates GNSS with cellular-based positioning methods. While GNSS excels in open environments, it struggles in urban or indoor settings due to signal degradation or blockage. Cellular-based positioning in hybrid systems effectively addresses these challenges and helps decrease the time needed to find the first position, ensuring consistent and accurate location information across diverse environments. Hybrid positioning systems intelligently incorporate data from these several sources, for instance, a hybrid system may place users in urban areas using cellular network-based locations while using GNSS for outdoor placement. The system may offer a smooth and reliable positioning experience in various settings by combining the data from these sources.

Applications for hybrid positioning include navigation systems, location-based services, asset tracking, augmented reality, and autonomous cars, all requiring precise and dependable placement. As can be analyzed in Fig. 1, locating the object using both technologies in the same algorithm is possible.

5G includes many capabilities that may help to increase the efficiency and accuracy of location [91]. The advantages of 5G for hybrid positioning are as follows:

- **Enhanced Network-based Positioning:** Greater location precision is offered by 5G networks than by earlier ones. With the advent of 5G, network operators can provide more accurate location data thanks to improved signal processing methods and better network infrastructure density. It will permit more precise triangulation from cell towers and improved localization in populated regions.
- **Multi-Connectivity:** 5G devices can connect to 5G and GNSS networks simultaneously. Hybrid positioning systems may use many positioning methods simultaneously because of their multi-connectivity capability. The total precision and dependability of location determination may be significantly enhanced by combining data from many sources, such as 5G network-based positioning, GNSS.
- **Low-Latency Communications:** Data transfer between the device and the network is quick because of 5G ultra-low latency. This reduced latency is especially useful for real-time positioning applications that demand quick updates. For instance, 5G low-latency transmission provides prompt and accurate position updates in autonomous cars and drones, promoting safer and more effective navigation.

In [92], ITS and V2X communications, the hybrid positioning approach combining 5G and GNSS technologies presents an innovative solution for obtaining high-precision location data essential for the advanced functionalities of autonomous vehicles. Integrating the URLLC and high-bandwidth capabilities of 5G with the broad spatial coverage of GNSS addresses the inherent limitations of each technology when used independently. 5G networks, with their dense infrastructure and edge computing capabilities, offer significant improvements in urban and indoor environments where GNSS signals are often weak or obstructed. This synergistic approach ensures continuous and accurate positioning information, even in challenging scenarios such as urban canyons or covered areas, where 5G or GNSS alone may fail. Furthermore, using 5G for real-time data transmission and processing allows rapidly disseminating GNSS correction data, further increasing positioning accuracy. This hybrid model elevates the reliability and accuracy of location-based services in ITS and makes way for innovative applications in traffic management, emergency response, and vehicle infrastructure interactions, strengthening the foundation of a truly interconnected and intelligent network.

Finally, in [93], it is an expanding field in response to growing demands for accurate location tracking in diverse environments. The paper presents an innovative approach by integrating doubly differentiated 5G technology with undifferentiated and doubly differentiated GPS observations. This integration aims to overcome the limitations inherent in traditional GNSS, particularly their ineffectiveness in complex indoor environments due to signal attenuation and obstruction. The algorithm proposed addresses a significant challenge in 5G technology: clock synchronization errors at base stations, which can negatively impact positioning accuracy. By incorporating reference terminals, this algorithm effectively minimizes these errors, improving the accuracy of positioning data between terminals and base stations and even between the base stations themselves. The comprehensive experiments cover various GPS positioning models such as SPP, PPP, RTD, and RTK. The study meticulously compares these models in different scenarios with traditional GPS-only systems. The results are convincing; the integrated system consistently outperforms the GPS-only configuration regarding accuracy, stability, and convergence speed. This is particularly notable in environments with physical obstructions, where GPS systems typically struggle. The document highlights the potential of 5G in improving GNSS performance and the importance of adapting to the growing demands of outdoor navigation. The findings contribute significantly to the field of positioning technology, suggesting that the fusion of 5G and GPS could be the key to unlocking more reliable and accurate navigation solutions.

A multiple-rate adaptive Kalman filter (MRAKF) for GNSS-5G hybrid location is introduced in [94]. By tackling issues with multi-rate fusion and the dynamic range of 5G measurement noise uncertainty, the goal is to improve positioning accuracy. The MRAKF algorithm adaptively modifies the observation noise covariance while allowing the fusion of GNSS and 5G measurements at various data speeds using a distance-dependent model. Additionally, a switchover technique is included to modify the placement mode according to the accessibility of base stations with the line of sight. The study assesses the proposed approach using simulations and an actual driving test. The extended Kalman filter (EKF) and four additional adaptive noise estimation techniques are compared in the simulations together with the performance of the MRAKF approach. The outcomes show that the MRAKF approach offers low computational cost, resilience in mixed LOS/NLOS settings, and a considerable improvement in positioning accuracy. The actual driving test further proves the method's success in enhancing both vertical and horizontal positioning accuracy.

In conclusion, the multi-rate fusion and 5G measurement noise uncertainty issues with GNSS-5G hybrid positioning are satisfactorily addressed by the suggested MRAKF approach. Regarding positioning precision, resilience, and real-time capabilities, it exceeds conventional EKF and alternative adaptive noise estimating techniques. This study recommends future research and advances the development of practical GNSS-5G fusion positioning algorithms.

The work enabled by [95] aims to integrate 5G cellular positioning with GNSS to enable high-precision positioning for applications like driverless cars. The authors suggest a condensed method termed physical-layer abstraction that makes it simpler to simulate GNSS and 5G range observables at the system level. Using simulations, the researchers assess the positioning capabilities of GNSS and 5G down-link time-difference of arrival (DL-TDoA) in urban macro-cell settings. The study aims to evaluate the positioning capacities of GNSS and 5G DL-TDoA in urban settings and determine the prerequisites for accurate positioning. The authors suggest a physical-layer abstraction approach, modeling GNSS faults with a Gaussian distribution considering the User Equivalent Range Error amount. They use a two-step process to estimate range errors for 5G observables. The receiving 5G signals were simulated to do so, and the cumulative density function (CDF) of errors per signal-to-noise level was interpolated. The simulation findings show that adopting hybrid systems, which incorporate several GNSS constellations and 5G DL-TDoA with a 100-MHz bandwidth, may achieve a

horizontal positioning accuracy below 5 m in outdoor urban contexts for 95% of situations. Based on their findings, the authors conclude that the hybridization of GNSS and 5G is crucial for meeting the high-accuracy positioning requirements in urban environments. The proposed physical-layer abstraction method simplifies system-level simulations and enables the assessment of positioning capabilities. However, further research is needed to target even higher accuracy levels, such as sub-meter accuracy in 99% of cases.

[96] aims to evaluate the performance of a hybrid positioning solution that combines 5G cellular technologies with GNSS in urban environments. The suggested three-dimensional city map simulation approach determines the line-of-sight conditions between receivers and transmitters. The study evaluates the possibilities of a hybrid 5G RTT and multi-constellation GNSS solution in a steep urban canyon. The simulation findings show that standalone GNSS solutions are greatly enhanced when a single 5G RTT measurement is combined with GNSS observables. The hybrid positioning method consistently achieves less than 10 meters of horizontal accuracy in dense metropolitan settings. In conclusion, the simulation employing 3D city maps to develop the proposed hybrid 5G and GNSS positioning system shows promise in improving positioning availability and accuracy in urban settings. Standalone GNSS location constraints are solved via 5G RTT and GNSS observables.

The research in [97] suggests a hybrid measurement strategy to handle the localization issues in a 5G-enabled GNSS. The goal is to determine if adding 5G observations to GNSS measurements can improve localization performance, particularly in areas without satellites. The proposed technique incorporates GNSS pseudo-ranges, GNSS carrier phases, 5G angle-of-departures, and 5G channel delays to estimate the user's position. The three key processes are getting the float solution, dealing with ambiguities, and getting the fixed solution. The technique uses a variety of metrics to increase location estimate accuracy. Several simulations were run to assess how well the suggested method works. These simulations evaluate the carrier-phase ambiguity resolution success rate and the estimated inaccuracy of the user's position when 5G observations are included. The findings show that using 5G observations makes localization possible even in situations with few visible satellites. The suggested approach significantly lowers estimate error and raises the success rate of carrier-phase ambiguity resolution. It works exceptionally well in areas with little satellite coverage when just a few satellites are visible.

In order to increase accuracy and availability in GNSS environments with obstructions, [98] investigates the hybridization of GNSS with 5G positioning. The goal is to use the precision and accessibility of 5G signals under challenging situations, including urban canyons, to get around the constraints of standalone GNSS. The suggested method incorporates GNSS receivers receiving assistance from 5G mmWave communication technologies. In the study, the parameterization of signals from GNSS satellites and 5G base stations is discussed, and based on these parameters, get the information on location and velocity. In a case study, GNSS and 5G location hybridization for autonomous vehicles (AVs) are discussed in conditions with a low geometric dilution of precision (GDOP) and restricted GNSS visibility. Simulations are run to assess the efficacy of the hybrid system in scenarios including urban streets with subpar GNSS geometry. The simulations adjust for visibility restrictions in the scenario by considering the availability of GNSS satellites and 5G base stations. The simulation findings show that in urban street situations with subpar GNSS geometry, the hybridization of GNSS with 5G positioning significantly increases positioning availability and accuracy. The total performance is improved by minimizing the shortcomings of solo GNSS by adding 5G signals as a backup system or filling reception gaps. The article concludes that a viable solution to positioning issues in GNSS environments with obstructions is the hybridization of GNSS and 5G positioning. The findings suggest that integrating GNSS and 5G is a solution, especially for systems incorporating autonomous cars.

[99] is another work that uses 5G small cells to enhance accurate location under challenging situations. The suggested approach combines base stations at the positional level and applies a Kalman filter (KF) with a dynamically tuned covariance matrix (DTCM) for improved sensor fusion. The methodology considers the geometry and connectivity of the BSs to solve linearization flaws of conventional extended Kalman filter (EKF) approaches. A case study was done in Toronto, Canada, to assess the effectiveness of the suggested strategy. The setup used in the case study aims to replicate real-world conditions to a certain extent. Compared to GPS PPP, simulations in a 5G simulator based on ray tracing evaluate the method's accuracy in urban canyons. The outcomes demonstrate that the suggested technique outperforms GPS PPP and EKF-based fusion methods in terms of positioning accuracy. The RMS, maximum, and 95% errors show sub-meter accuracy. In conclusion, the positioning accuracy under challenging settings is greatly improved by incorporating 5G small cells at the positioning level with a dynamically modified covariance matrix in the Kalman filter. According to this study, GNSS-based positioning may one day be replaced by 5G technology for precision applications. The summarized result of this vast research can be observed in Table 9.

In summary, the discussion of autonomous driving and V2X communication underlines the essential role of precise localization for vehicle safety, coordination, and decision-making in dynamic environments. Our exploration of hybrid GNSS and 5G positioning highlights how advanced localization techniques ensure the accuracy and immediacy required for V2X message exchanges in these autonomous systems.

However, a reliable infrastructure is essential to achieve these high localization and real-time communication standards. Private 5G networks emerge as a necessary enabler of this framework, providing dedicated, low-latency communication that public networks can not sustain. They offer a controlled environment with customizable network resources to support V2X applications. Next Chapter 4 will explore how these private 5G networks can effectively support V2X communication, boosting spectrum allocations and configurations needed to support autonomous driving solutions, setting them as foundational to the future of connected.

4. Technology overview

The preceding sections highlighted V2X communication, ITS, and precise localization as core elements of connected vehicle ecosystems. To fully realize the potential of these technologies, an infrastructure capable of supporting their demanding requirements is essential.

The advent of 5G networks offers a critical foundation [100] that enhances speed, latency, and network capacity over previous generations. 5G enables real-time data exchange, low-latency communication, and massive connectivity, which are all essential for V2X applications and ITS. By facilitating high-speed and reliable connections, 5G ensures the responsiveness and precision that autonomous driving and advanced localization demand.

In addition to supporting the automotive sector, 5G technology is integral to the more expansive landscape of intelligent infrastructure. This includes applications in smart cities, healthcare, and Internet of Things (IoT), which demand scalable, high-throughput communication. Thus, 5G is a foundational technology for V2X, ITS, and an array of interconnected systems, facilitating the development of next-generation, intelligent, and responsive environments.

The 3GPP, following a consensus-based approach, is responsible for developing specifications for 3G, 4G, and 5G technologies. In early 2019, the 3GPP finalized Release 15 (Rel. 15 or R15) specifications, marking the first round of 5G standards. Rel. 15 establishes the groundwork for URLLC and principally concentrates on Enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB). It adds assistance for low-latency demands. The next release, Rel. 16, which served as the second phase of 5G standards, was finished in July 2020. Rel. 16 adds new capabilities such

Table 9
Comparison of the Hybrid positioning techniques.

Algorithm	Input Data Type	Simulation Type	Environment	Error
[94] Multiple-Rate adaptive Kalman filter (MRAKF)	Distance dependent model, ToA, AoA, LOS	Realistic	Outdoor in suburban	< 1 m
[95] Hybrid GNSS and 5G DL-TDoA positioning	LOS conditions, SNR levels DL-TDoA,	Simulation	Outdoor in urban	< 5 m
[96] Hybrid 5G RTT and multi-constellation GNSS solution	Sky visibility, RTT, LoS con-ditions	Simulation	Outdoor in deep urban canyon	< 10 m
[98] GNSS receivers + 5G mmWave	ToA, LOS conditions	Simulation	Outdoor in urban canyons or underground tunnels in vehicles	< 1 m
[99] hybrid 5G BSs through a DTCCM-KF method	Sky conditions, AOD, RTT	Simulation	Outdoor in Urban and canyons downtown in vehicles areas	< 2 m

as non-public networks, New Radio (NR) unlicensed, NR positioning, and Integrated Access and Backhaul (IAB), in addition to improving the features already provided in the previous release [101]. Then Rel. 17, which was established in 2022, added new features like NR operation extended to 71GHz, NR over Non terrestrial Networks (NTN), IOT over NTN, UE power-saving enhancements for NR, coverage and positioning enhancements, enhanced support of non-public networks [102]. The 3GPP is now working to standardize a more recent version, Rel. 18 [103]. When this document was written, the study phase of Rel. 19 started.

5G is more adaptable than its predecessors, thanks to Software-Defined Networking (SDN) and Network Function Virtualization (NFV). SDN allows quicker network alterations without interfering with data transport by separating the control and data planes. NFV creates network services like firewalls and routers using software, rather than dedicated hardware. By splitting a single physical network into several virtual networks, each virtual network has dedicated resources. I.e., network slicing preserves speed and security while enabling a wide range of services. By processing data locally, edge computing lowers latency for real-time applications such as autonomous vehicles and augmented reality.

As 5G technology continues to evolve with successive 3GPP releases, it also acts as an enabler for implementing 5G private networks. The deployment of these private networks greatly depends on 5G's adaptability, which these technologies enable.

4.1. Public or private 5G networks for V2X

Both public and private 5G networks offer unique advantages for the V2X applications and autonomous driving. These networks are particularly effective in addressing the specific demands of vehicular communication, such as ultra-low latency, high reliability, and seamless connectivity [104]. However, these networks differ significantly in deployment for V2X scenarios, especially considering cost and management complexity.

Public 5G Networks are managed by MNO and provide broad coverage, making them an attractive option for V2X applications that require extensive reach. They offer the advantage of being maintained by operators who invest in infrastructure upgrades, ensure regulatory compliance, and deliver connectivity across large geographic areas. However, this type of network can suffer bandwidth limitations due to shared usage with other kinds of services, potentially impacting performance in high-density areas. The shared infrastructure of public networks may not always meet the latency and bandwidth requirements for V2X applications [2], especially during peak usage hours when other public users may congest the network.

In contrast, Private 5G Networks (Non-Public Networks, or NPNs) are dedicated networks set up specifically for enterprises or specific applications, offering tailored control over network parameters. For V2X, private 5G networks are especially advantageous as they can guarantee dedicated bandwidth and security protocols for V2X

communication [105]. This customization allows for uninterrupted service supporting autonomous driving or emergency V2V communication, without the risk of public network congestion. According to findings in various studies, private 5G networks enable operators to better control costs, performance, and coverage within specific, defined areas, thereby enhancing network efficiency for V2X applications [106, 107].

Private 5G networks provide reliability, a critical point for V2X, by ensuring that communication channels are not shared with non-critical applications. This isolation reduces the risk of packet loss or delay during high-demand periods. On the other hand, public 5G networks are generally reliable but may not meet the benchmarks required for high-level V2X applications in all settings. Moreover, public networks face regulatory constraints and may not offer the same degree of customization and control that a private network affords. This could be a limiting factor in dynamic V2X scenarios [104].

Another point this work mentions is the need for V2X and autonomous driving for precise and reliable localization, critical for real-time maneuvering in autonomous and semi-autonomous driving scenarios. Public 5G networks provide a broad base of connectivity capable of supporting the requirements. However, they may struggle with high precision and ultra-low latency needed for real-time vehicle positioning under all conditions. Private 5G networks, by contrast, can better integrate localization, such as real-time GNSS corrections and hybrid positioning techniques.

From a cost perspective, private 5G networks represent a higher initial capital expenditure (CapEx) due to the need for dedicated infrastructure and maintenance staff. However, this model can pay off in long-term operational expenditures (OpEx) savings, particularly when network slicing and virtualization techniques are employed to optimize resource allocation. These technologies are essential to private 5G networks and enable savings by facilitating efficient use of available spectrum and infrastructure. Studies have shown that, over time, private 5G networks can reduce total cost of ownership by up to 53% compared to traditional public networks, depending on the extent of virtualization and automation implemented [2,106,108].

In summary, while public 5G networks provide a cost-effective solution with more coverage, private 5G networks offer a more reliable and customizable option for V2X applications where latency, dedicated bandwidth, and security are paramount. Private networks offer reliability and tailored service quality, combining lower long-term operational costs.

4.2. Private networks - A Deep discussion on V2X scenarios

5G Private networks are set to improve the digitization and real-time networking of Industry 4.0. They are critical because they enable smooth communication and data sharing across network-connected devices. This section examines the impact of 5G private networks on process automation and data insights. This requires the existence of highly reliable communications systems that can operate in an (almost)

cable-free environment since various devices must roam freely, such as automated guided vehicles in factories or autonomous driving cars on roads (which are still part of the industry 4.0 process, considering, for example, trucks transporting cargo from one factory to another). These networks differ substantially from conventional networking systems regarding service requirements [109].

Although satellite technologies can work as an extension of the main technology, they cannot act as the principal technology due to (i) the high latency of the communications link and (ii) the occurrence of non-line-of-sight for long periods. Consequently, viable alternatives are narrowed to Wi-Fi and 5G. Both are competitors in what concerns technologies for vehicular communications, especially in V2V communications due to their direct and short-link nature. Still, performing well in radio handover scenarios gives a clear advantage to 5G in V2I cases. There is a need to establish 5G links between V2X cases. Still, these can be public, i.e., working in a particular spectrum whose utilization license a given operator purchased or private. The main advantage of these so-called private networks is that they can be tailor-based for specialized infrastructure and have customized settings [110]. The following advantages result from using this strategy:

- **Dedicated Coverage:** Private 5G networks offer exclusive coverage within designated buildings or areas, ensuring uninterrupted connectivity in remote locations or those with weak public network infrastructure.

- **Exclusive Capacity:** With a private 5G network, there is no contention for resources as experienced in public systems. The available capacity is solely allocated to the private network, eliminating congestion caused by other network users.
- **Intrinsic Control:** Private 5G networks provide owners total control over their devices, which is impossible with public systems. Operators may improve security and data privacy by implementing their security standards, regulating user access, prioritizing traffic, and, most crucially, ensuring that sensitive data stays on their property.
- **Customized Service:** To adapt to particular industrial applications, private 5G networks enable customization. On public networks, this level of personalization is not possible. Industrial applications may also effectively share a private 5G network, enabling optimal resource use.
- **Dependable Communication:** Incorporating customization, intrinsic control, and support for ultra-reliable low-latency communication, the devoted nature of private 5G networks enables dependable wireless communication for industrial use cases while enhancing operational dependability.

By understanding the fundamentals of private 5G networks, it is now possible to analyze the architecture that underpins these systems, their designs, the offered security, and the personalized connectivity.

Fig. 11. Private Mobile Networks: Deployment Options (adapted from [111]).

4.3. Overview of 5G private network architecture

When deploying a private 5G network, it is crucial to consider several variables, such as spectrum allocation, network ownership and operation, and the degree of trust between private and public network operators. There are different ways to deploy the 5G network, in [111] shows its various architectures. Four different architectures deserve to be mentioned in this work.

A private 5G network in Stand-Alone (SA) deployment operates independently and establishes a personal 5G network that functions independently of an already-established public network infrastructure, Fig. 11(A). Therefore, the private network performs as a SA system, offering connectivity and services inside a particular area or company. Another type of deployment can be Shared Radio access network (RAN) with Public Network Integrated, shown in Fig. 11(B), where the private and public 5G networks share part of the RAN while the core network functions are separated. The data flow in the Private Network is restricted to that zone. Only the base stations from the private part can be configured. An additional type of deployment is a Shared RAN and Control Plane with a Public Network Integrated, Fig. 11(C), where the private network shares part of the RAN and the public network controls the network. Nevertheless, the private network's whole traffic flow stays inside certain boundaries. Lastly, Fig. 11(D) shows a deployment type with Hosted by the Public Network, where the public network hosts all the networks. All the traffic flows outside of the defined premises. In Fig. 11, it is possible to analyze all the different deployments.

Spectrum choice will be essential for using private networks with these architectures. Much of the spectrum has already been allocated to specific use cases or bought outright by public network operators, who then use it for their purposes.

Government authorities can use the dedicated unlicensed spectrum as an alternative. Furthermore, there is a great deal of potential for the unlicensed spectrum to support the quick development of private networks. This work will mainly focus on exploring the possibilities of the unlicensed spectrum, which will be presented in the next section.

4.4. New radio unlicensed (NR-U)

The 5 GHz range is just one of several frequency bands within which NR-U can work. The specifics of each band will be discussed in more detail in Section 4.4.1. It is important to note that local spectrum allocations and regional regulatory constraints may influence the specific frequency bands available by NR-U. The NR-U mode of operation was introduced in 3GPP Release 16 [112] to enable unlicensed spectrum integration into 5G networks for cellular operations. This mode allows for such possibilities as dynamic Time-division duplexing (TDD), beamforming, and wide-band carriers in unlicensed bands for uplink and downlink use.

Even though it has its benefits, NR-U has some limitations compared to standard NR in the licensed spectrum. These limitations are crucial when creating applications that utilize these technologies. One of

those limitations is the interference with other networks that share the same spectrum, which can be reduced if some methods are used based on the signal intensity and bandwidth. Given the many technologies with which NR-U coexists, cooperative methods are necessary. As a result, NR-U signifies a remarkable leap forward in technology by building up. NR-U builds upon the design of the physical and Media Access Control layer (MAC) layers, replacing LTE-LAA [113]. Due to the shared nature of this spectrum, it has several limitations and constraints throughout working in the range of 5.150 GHz to

6.425 GHz. Wi-Fi and other wireless technologies often use this range of bands. Some of the features of the bands in the unlicensed spectrum are shown in Fig. 12.

Some studies have suggested higher frequency values [114], especially in situations where intra-network License-Assisted Access (LAA) Listen Before Talk (LBT) device co-existence is critical, such as in dense deployment scenarios related to 5G NR-U. The study's conclusion emphasizes the importance of considering various class priorities and how those priorities may affect communication latency, failure rate, and channel efficiency. This understanding helps create 5G NR-U systems with more effective channel access techniques.

The literature presents some studies that show the 5G NR-U as part of the future and is vital in improving several sectors. In [115] and [116], the authors show that the NR-U brings crucial characteristics for future industrial networks. There are challenges on a shared spectrum that need to be resolved using methods such as shared maximum channel occupancy time, handover skipping, self-organized networks, adaptive backoff mechanism, and multi-domain coexistence approach. This type of mechanism makes it possible to have a design using NR-U spectrum, and the considerations for coverage, interference management, and throughput help meet the industry's specific requirements, which will be explored later in the document. The availability of this spectrum creates new opportunities for designing mechanisms and features to support bandwidth-intensive and latency-sensitive applications. A great effort is needed to get the performance close to the NR [117]. However, implementing interference control algorithms and spectrum management can improve the capacity of this type of network. The main issue is that NR does not serve specific business models (which only NR-U serves), and there is also the problem of NR spectrum saturation where NR-U is of utmost importance. So, the critical (and challenging) aspect is to achieve mechanisms that bring the quality of services running on NR-U closer to the quality of services running on NR.

The NR-U radio stack architecture is intended to provide seamless integration and convergence with NR services while reducing cost and complexity. The design is based on the NR radio stack with minor modifications and comprises layers such as Radio Resource Control (RRC), Service Data Adaptation Protocol (SDAP), Packet Data Convergence Protocol (PDCP), Radio Link Control (RLC), MAC, and PHY. There are challenges in implementing the NR-U, like the operation over multiple channels where NR-U employs UNII bands with primary 20 MHz channels, enabling more capacity by channel bonding, as mentioned in [118]. It allows operation on a single wideband carrier,

Fig. 12. Unii bands adapted to the Europe dedicated unlicensed bands.

which may overlap with unlicensed channels. NR-U supports multi-carrier channel access in standalone and non-standalone modes, allowing primary and secondary channel bonding, and also allows for solo operation for both master and secondary carriers in the unlicensed spectrum.

The Traffic Splitter (TS) block enables NR-U and other RANs to use variable traffic splitting/convergence algorithms. Depending on the NR-U deployment situation, TS can be placed at various levels within the radio stack. gNB-initiated Control Overhead Time (COT) may be separated into DL and UL bursts in NR-U's transmission and signal architecture. Control and data message exchange is facilitated by Physical Downlink Control Channel (PDCCH), Physical Uplink Control Channel (PUCCH), Physical Downlink Shared Channel (PDSCH), and PUSCH channels. The same OFDM-modulated waveform as NR is used in NR-U, which provides scalable numerology with varying subcarrier spacings. Control and data messages are sent in time intervals known as TTIs, and each TTI can hold up to two Transport Blocks (TBs). Because HARQ processes manage ACK feedback and retransmissions, continual TBs transmissions are possible. The numerology index defines the duration of NR-U transmissions and is divided into time slots. The CP extension is utilized for alignment and to give more time when moving between DL and UL. The RRC layer controls the CP extension, which addresses the sensing interval misalignment.

NR-U differs in non-standalone mode by providing standalone operation across unlicensed bands, allowing both master and secondary cells on unlicensed carriers. Another challenge is the frequency of NR-U/Wi-Fi coexistence, where choosing energy detection levels is a significant difficulty in NR-U design. Energy detection (ED) gives a binary indicator of channel occupancy, whereas preamble detection (PD) provides information on the device occupying the channel. Changing the detection threshold depending on device type can reduce hidden/exposed terminals and improve the fairness of coexisting technologies. Without additional technologies, the baseline ED threshold for a 20 MHz channel is -72 dBm, which can be relaxed to -62 dBm. It is critical to scale the ED threshold based on channel bandwidth [119]. RRC-configured UEs can change their thresholds within the constraints of regional spectrum laws, possibly allowing improved spatial frequency reuse via adaptive reinforcement learning. NR-U cells benefit from Radio Resource Management (RRM) and Radio Link Monitoring (RLM) for coordinated channel access. AP clustering and statistics monitoring can apply concepts similar to those of Wi-Fi networks, the CP-based signal detection scheme outlined in existing literature can enhance cross-technology signal detection for NR-U and Wi-Fi.

Both the DL and the UL scheduling in NR-U are asynchronous, necessitating explicit notification of the time for retransmitting failed TBs or code block groups (CBGs). Three temporal delays influence DL HARQ procedures: D0, D1, and D2, whereas U0 and U1 are critical delays for UL HARQ processes. D0 and U0 indicate the initial delay before expecting an ACK/NACK following a TB/CBG transmission, including processing and feedback preparation time. D1 and U1 denote the delays between receiving a NACK and scheduling a retransmission encompassing decision-making and preparation intervals. D2 may involve delays related to retransmissions or receiver processing time post-retransmission. Properly configuring these delays facilitates retransmissions, maximizes spectrum utilization efficiency, reduces interference, and boosts throughput for both NR-U and Wi-Fi systems. Effectively managing these parameters is vital for maintaining the coexistence of communication standards, ensuring that NR-U system can efficiently handle its transmissions and retransmissions in a shared environment, keeping these time delays inside the gNB-initiated/UE-initiated COT border.

The TBs can be broken into CBGs, allowing the PHY layer to handle TBs and CBG-based HARQ designs. More research is needed to determine the influence of these designs on NR-U/Wi-Fi coexistence. HARQ additions include dynamic codebook use, one-time feedback requests, and the option to specify the timing of ACK feedback as 'later.' Identify

events spanning many COTs, and PDSCH events are indexed using the DL assignment index (DLI) and PDSCH group bits. Because NR-U's UL scheduling considers unstable unlicensed channels, a single UL grant can schedule numerous UL TBs for the same UE. Configured UL grants allow UEs to utilize UL resources without a grant, decreasing signaling overhead and increasing channel access options. NR-U also allows transmitting sounding reference signals on every suitable UL OFDM symbol, facilitating wideband channel estimation. The literature contains detailed information on DL and UL resource mapping and allocation in NR-U.

In the RRC layer, the UE connects to the gNB with the strongest signal, where synchronization is maintained during initial access. Every 20 milliseconds, the discovery frame is broadcast periodically and contains SSB bursts that carry crucial data for UEs to attach to unlicensed cells. The discovery frame ensures speedy initial access. To find a cell, the UE watches for SSB instances. Depending on SCS, the discovery frame may occur in 10 or 20 possible locations during a 5-millisecond burst window. After receiving the discovery frame, the UE starts a Random Access Channel (RACH) procedure with the best gNB using a 2-message or 4-message handshake procedure, depending on connectivity status. There could be more than one COT in the RACH process. The periodicity of the RACH procedure and discovery frame is optimized to support correct initial access without interfering with IEEE 802.11 systems [120]. NR-U incorporates additional paging occasions to address channel unavailability. There are different ways to deploy the NR-U. In [112], three distinct ways are shown. There is Carrier Aggregation, Dual Connectivity, and the Standalone mode.

[120] and [121] thoroughly describe these different methods. The Carrier Aggregation method is considered where the unlicensed spectrum is used only to augment downstream user plane capacity. The Control Plane (CP) data is transported over NR licensed spectrum only. Then, the Dual Connectivity method supports upstream and downstream user plane traffic over the unlicensed spectrum. This is designed for traffic offload, not coverage, so control plane traffic is transported only over the licensed spectrum. The Carrier Aggregation mode improves throughput, while the Dual Connectivity mode enhances both throughput and reliability. However, the DC (Dual Connectivity) mode introduces the complexity of associating a UE with multiple cells. In the DC mode, if the master link fails, the secondary links remain unaffected. Depending on the utilization of DC and CA for connecting with UEs over unlicensed carriers, 3GPP provides flexible deployment options for NR-U. Finally, the last method is the Standalone, a mode of operation that relies solely on the unlicensed spectrum for control and user plane traffic. Apart from the deployments mentioned, other deployments are shown in Fig. 13.

Scenario A) shows that the CA mode comprises a licensed carrier provided by a 5G NR cell and an unlicensed carrier served by a 5G NR-U cell. Scenario B) demonstrates that the DC mode consists of a licensed carrier served by an LTE cell and an unlicensed carrier served by a 5G NR-U cell. The Standalone mode, essential for operating private networks, involves an unlicensed carrier(s) served by a 5G NR-U cell, represented in scenario C). Scenario D) shows the combination of a licensed carrier served by a 5G NR cell for uplink communication and an unlicensed carrier served by a 5G NR-U cell for downlink communication. Finally, in Scenario E), in DC mode, a licensed carrier is served by a 5G NR cell, while an unlicensed carrier is served by a 5G NR-U cell [122]. Table 10 shows a summary of the pros and cons of each of these deployments.

Literature such as [123] and [124] study the potential of spectrum usage regulation taxonomies for ITS in vehicular communications. It shows possible solutions for standards like DSRC, C-V2X, Wi-Fi standards, and the technical challenges and testbeds associated with each option. The NR-U systems must comply with spectrum regulations to ensure harmonious coexistence with other incumbents, such as Wi-Fi. The article presents three possible deployments the DSRC, C-V2X, and Wi-Fi with interference mitigation, or DSRC, and C-V2X with

Fig. 13. NR-U deployment scenarios (adapted from [120] [122],).

Table 10
Pros and Cons for different NR-U deployment scenarios.

Implementation Scenario	Pros	Cons
<i>Carrier Aggregation</i>	Increased data rates Enhanced user experience	Complexity and cost Interference concerns
<i>LTE Dual Connectivity</i>	Efficient spectrum utilization Seamless transition Improved coverage	Compatibility limitations Complexity and cost Interference and compatibility challenges
<i>Standalone Mode</i>	Enhanced capacity Native NR-U support Lower latency	Limited benefits for LTE-only devices Infrastructure requirements Interoperability challenges
<i>DL-UL Decoupling</i>	Flexibility and scalability Improved capacity management Enhanced user experience	Limited coverage Increased complexity Interference and synchronization challenges
<i>NR-NR Dual Connectivity</i>	Quality of Service differentiation Enhanced capacity and performance Seamless handover and mobility Flexibility and efficiency	Device support Deployment complexity Interference and compatibility issues Limited device support

interoperation or C-V2X only. The interoperability between DSRC and C-V2X is identified as the most complex technical challenge. The choice of spectrum usage regulation taxonomies will depend on each country’s specific plans and priorities involved in standardization.

Sidelink Communication allows for direct communication between V2V and V2I; this technology can make maximum use of the NR-U. This facilitates sharing real-time vital messages such as road conditions, dangers, and potential accidents, thereby enhancing road safety and efficiency. Sidelink follows specific protocols that ensure efficient and reliable sidelink conversations while considering factors such as latency (speed of delivery), information security, and efficient use of the radio spectrum. The technology allows the UE to be used as a gNB for other UE, causing their communication. For this to work, several channel access mechanisms must be implemented so that the radio spectrum is shared among vehicles in an orderly manner without congestion involving all road users. NR-U is being researched into [125,126], where these bands have several benefits for this communication. Shorter-range communications at higher frequencies cause signals to attenuate more rapidly, making them ideal for local communication between nearby vehicles and infrastructure, reducing interference with long-haul cellular traffic. Above all else, they are critical because these bands are now available worldwide, making them a viable option for standardizing V2X deployments.

As seen so far, NR-U brings a severe problem with interference between signals, and for that, different methods can be applied. LBT can significantly affect channel efficiency and latency, especially when timely message transmission is critical. LBT is increasingly important in applications like IOT networks, because of its more straightforward implementation and less resource usage. On the other hand, other algorithms, such as Cooperative Multipoint (CoMP), are required in vehicular networks where latency minimization is crucial. Despite being more intricate and requiring more resources, these algorithms guarantee optimal performance and minimal delay. The Section 4.4.2 will explain these interference reduction algorithms more thoroughly.

4.4.1. Regulation bodies

Different countries and regions designate specific frequency channels or sub-bands for NR-U operation within the spectrum. Regulatory bodies choose the frequencies and standards for NR-U operation based on spectrum availability, interference control, and compatibility with other wireless technologies.

Any device or operator can use this frequency band if it complies with the regulations and usage rules set by the regulatory bodies. By using unlicensed spectrum, operators can use NR to provide 5G connectivity in areas where licensed spectrum is saturated or unavailable or to give connection to small businesses like factories, universities (campus), IoT Agriculture systems, and more. Countries and regions may have different frequency channels or sub-bands designated for NR-U operation in the spectrum; for example, there are different legislations for each world area, including the USA, EU, China, and Russia.

In the EU, legislation related to the automotive spectrum and applications follows specific guidelines. In the context of connected vehicles and ITS, there are two distinct groups: critical and non-critical systems. The EU has defined specific spectrum bands for critical ITS systems requiring high reliability and safety. In the public spectrum band, the

2.6 GHz range is reserved for critical ITS communications. This frequency band enables the implementation of C-V2X communication services for applications requiring fast response times and reliable communications in safety-critical situations. In addition, the EU has also designated the 5.8 GHz spectrum band for critical ITS communications on a confidential basis [8].

Different ways to set the radio bands on the unlicensed spectrum, such as Unlicensed National Information Infrastructure (U-NII), can give us that information. These bands are intended to provide additional spectrum for unlicensed use, which helps promote innovation without the need for individual licenses. The U-NII bands are divided into sub-bands or channels, each with specific frequency ranges typically operating in the 2.4 GHz and 5 GHz [127].

The detailed U-NII bands information for its use and the comparison with the EU legislation can be analyzed in Table 11, where it is shown different bands, services location, and their restrictions.

Table 11
NR-U bands with the dedicated services and legislation associated.

Freq. Range [MHz]	Band	Service char.	Restrictions	EU legislation
5 150 to 5 250	U-NII-1	Indoor and outdoor	Outdoor installation cannot be fixed	2022/179/EU
5 250 to 5 350	U-NII-2a	Indoor use only	Installations in road vehicles not permitted	
5 470 to 5 725	U-NII-2c	Indoor and outdoor	Installations in road vehicles not permitted	
5 725 to 5 875	U-NII-2c		Non-specific short-range equipment	2019/1345/EU
5 795 to 5 815	U-NII-3		Road toll applications and intelligent tachograph applications, weights and dimensions	2019/1345/EU
5 855 to 5 875	U-NII-4	ITS non-safety applications		ECC/REC/(08)01 2019/1345/EU
5 865 to 5 875	U-NII-4	ITS non-safety applications	V2V, V2I, and infrastructure-to-vehicle systems	2019/1345/EU
5 875 to 5 915	U-NII-4	ITS road safety-related applications		2020/1426/EU
5 915 to 5 925	U-NII-4	ITS road safety-related applications	Limited to applications involving I2V connectivity only	
5 945 to 6 425	U-NII-5	Indoor and outdoor	Outdoor use must be very low power to cover short-range applications for small area direct communications.	2021/1067/EU

This Table 11 shows that the only band compliant with certain vehicular use cases is U-NII-4. This work will focus on using NR-U in vehicular communication, but there is a more dedicated spectrum for other areas that can be seen on [128]. For critical vehicular communications, the EU legislation limits the maximum channel bandwidth to 10 MHz in this band and the maximum total transmit power to 33 dBm with a transmit power control (TPC) range of at least 30 dB. More dedicated bandwidth exists for non-critical vehicular communications, but the signal characteristics remain the same.

The distribution of the 5 GHz unlicensed spectrum varies among nations, each with unique regulations and usage restrictions. There is notable availability in the USA, China, South Korea, Europe, Japan, and India for the 5.15–5.35 GHz (UNII-1 and U-NII-2A) band. It is possible to access the 5.47–5.725 GHz (U-NII-2C) spectrum in the USA, South Korea, Europe, and Japan. The USA, China, South Korea, and India also have unrestricted access to the 5.725–5.85 GHz (U-NII-3) band. The unlicensed 5.15–5.35 GHz and

5.47–5.85 GHz bands in the United States and Canada support wireless access. On the other hand, these bands are reserved for the Wireless Access System (WAS) and Radio Local Area Networks (RLANs) in Europe and Japan. China uses the 5.15–5.35 GHz band for interior applications and the 5.725–5.85 GHz band for outdoor ones. The 5.35–5.47 GHz (U-NII-2B) and 5.85–5.925 GHz (U-NII-4) bands in the USA and Canada. For example, the FCC proposed in its Notice of Proposed Rulemaking (NPRM) 13–22 to open up 195 MHz in the 5.35–5.47 GHz band for radar system mergers and in the 5.85–5.925 GHz band for ITS mergers. The European Commission has also proposed using WAS/RLANs on the 5.725–5.85 GHz spectrum for Fixed Wireless Access (FWA).

4.4.2. Mechanisms of interference reduction

As can be inferred from what has been described, one serious

problem in using NR-U is the interference between different technologies, such as WiFi, that fall in the same network spectrum. So, developing contention mechanisms is needed to diminish the interference and packet loss that can become a severe problem in several use cases. There are several interference types, like Co-Channel Interference and Adjacent Channel Interference [124]. When NR-U emissions from one channel cross into nearby channels, adjacent channel interference occurs. This interference may be caused by poor filtering or insufficient guard bands between neighboring channels, which will cause signals to overlap and degrade the quality of the adjoining channel. It occurs when many NR-U cells or nodes using the same channel interfere with one another. Reduced data and higher error rates might result from this interference, affecting signal quality and overall system performance.

A channel access method is considered LBT in use by NR-U to operate over unlicensed UNII bands below 7 GHz. These open and shared frequency bands mean coexistence with technologies like LTE-LAA or IEEE 802.11 is possible. Devices determine when to transmit by listening for several idle slots proportional to a contention window (CW). This approach takes after the CSMA/CA protocol, which employs an exponential backoff mechanism, to adaptively set the size of CW depending on the network status.

Collusion rates and channel access latency are two essential network performance parameters directly affecting the contention windows. Two parameters define CW: CWmin and CWmax, which are the lower minimum and upper maximum limits for the size of the Contention Window, respectively. At first, the window size doubles from CWmin after every failed attempt until it reaches CWmax, significantly reducing repeated collisions in congested areas only. One of the key technologies used by IEEE 802.11 (Wi-Fi) systems is Enhanced Distributed Channel Access (EDCA). This technique prioritizes traffic into four categories, characterized by different CWmin, CWmax, and Arbitration Interframe Space (AIFS) values. This setting accommodates various application needs, such as voice calls with minimal delays and bulk data transfer. Other features like Transmission Opportunity (TXOP) periods and block acknowledgments enhance throughput and efficiency. On top of that, enhancements brought about in IEEE 802.11ax include Uplink/Downlink (UL/DL) split with Orthogonal Frequency-Division Multiple Access (OFDMA). These improvements further enhance network efficiency while allowing more devices to be supported.

LTE-LAA and NR-U have established LBT Categories (CATs), which are used to differentiate between different channel access schemes. LTE-LAA and NR-U mainly adopt CAT4-LBT, which has similarities with CSMA/CA mechanisms. In this case, contention window size is adjusted dynamically based on network feedback to achieve better coexistence with other systems in the unlicensed spectrum. NR-U also has multiple priority classes similar to the EDCA mechanism in Wi-Fi, enabling differentiated traffic handling according to its priority levels.

To ensure a more deterministic or critical communication, CAT2-LBT can provide semi-static channel access, which is crucial for transmitting important and time-sensitive frames. The operational dynamics like timing, UL/DL configurations, and Hybrid Automatic Repeat Request (HARQ) processes in LTE-LAA and NR-U have differences that are related to their adaptation to unlicensed spectrum requirements.

NR-U is uniquely designed for gNB-initiated COT for dynamic UL/DL switching to enhance flexibility and resource use efficiency. However, the system currently supports only UL-to-DL switching from the user equipment side. In these systems, control channels and data channels (PDCCHs and PDSCHs for downlink control and data, PUCCH and PUSCH for uplink control and data transmissions, respectively) are vital elements that enable effective communication between network part radios with UE at boundaries of licensed radio bands as well as other possibilities of such unlicensed spectrum-based services.

The type of synchronism or asynchronism is essential, depending on the chosen use case. Choosing a type of asynchronism is of the utmost importance, such as the reliability of the service is terrible, as it is always waiting and only then occupies the channel and sends. In some cases, it

may not send anything during some time. With a synchronous system, it is possible to maintain order between the waiting and sending times, thus resulting in greater efficiency for its use. In Fig. 14, it is possible to verify the behaviour of both types of spectrum sharing.

Some types of methods were created to diminish the interference, such as the asynchronous spectrum sharing type (e.g., LBT and some divergent from it like omniLBT, dirLBT, pairLBT, and LBTswitch [130]), as well as of the synchronous spectrum sharing type, such as CoMP.

The LBT mechanism is employed by unlicensed devices, such as Wi-Fi and NR-U, to ensure fair spectrum sharing and minimize interference with other devices [124]. It requires a device to check for active broadcasts on the channel before starting its transmission. Devices can prevent interfering with other technologies using the same unlicensed frequency bands by using LBT.

[124] presents a vast literature with several vital points explaining different methods of interference management, like the LBT used in previous 3GPP-defined unlicensed technologies, and it will always depend on the regulation of the implemented zone. Research challenges related to coexistence, interference, and harmonious operation are identified. This study makes a significant point for applying NR-U in the vehicular world. There is a continuing study in the literature on neighbouring channel interference and how it may affect applications made possible by V2X communications. However, the importance of this interference is still up for debate. Therefore, it is crucial to undertake research that shows whether unlicensed devices can function in the U-NII band's lower channels without impairing the functionality of V2X Radio Access Technologies (RATs). There is a need for testbeds where it is possible to simulate environments with factors such as device density and locations for both V2X and unlicensed devices, typical transmit powers of V2X, and unlicensed transmitters. These realistic propagation models reflect real-world scenarios. This will be the most important to prove the reliability of this service with this dedicated spectrum.

[122] proposes a simulation to evaluate the different LBT-based channel access procedures for NR-U/Wi-Fi indoor mmWave coexistence scenarios is also provided. It presents different requirements for the harmonization of 5 GHz usage. This network needs to follow the LBT, the Maximum Channel Occupancy Time (MCOT) where the system can not make continuous transmissions, and the existence of limits that a device can use. For others, such as Dynamic Frequency Selection (DFS) functionality that avoids interfering between 5 GHz and 60 GHz radar systems, the objective is to spread the traffic load across the different channels uniformly. This work simulates different scenarios to test different LBT specifications. This shows that the traditional methods are

insufficient for this kind of solution. Hence, the LBT for the NR-U had to be improved using other methods like the LBT for Beam-Based Transmissions, Receiver-Assisted LBT for Beam-Based Transmissions, Intra-RAT Tight Frequency Reuse and Congestion Window Size (CWS) Adjustment for Beam-Based Transmissions. In summary, the research demonstrates that incorporating receiver feedback enhances coexistence performance in 5G NR-U, improving QoS and fairness. Regarding the COT structures, it is found that slots with multiple DL/UL switching points within the COT are better suited for NR-U. For the initial access in NR-U, careful design considerations are discussed for SS block design, RACH procedure, and paging procedure to address the requirements of LBT effectively) and Out-of-Channel Blocking (OCB). These considerations aim to optimize the performance and efficiency of 5G NR-U regarding coexistence and initial access.

Other studies, such as [131], show different approaches to the interference fairness between Wi-Fi and NR-U where they propose a ML model to channel allocation. It was used as a testbed created and evaluated where legacy methods were tested to compare with their approach. The result shows that the approach is beneficial for long synchronization periods since the behaviour between Wi-Fi and NR-U converges for short synchronization periods. This work was not conclusive, but it leaves a loophole that can be studied.

However, these algorithms are insufficient to cover cases such as networks with autonomous vehicles, so other methods are needed. Such methods of Synchronous spectrum sharing like the technology of CoMP are applied in 5G networks to improve coverage, capacity, and performance. Multiple base stations or cells coordinate their transmission and reception in this situation. It can increase system efficiency, reduce interference, and improve signal quality. Even while CoMP does not address technology interference specifically, its advantages in terms of interference reduction can indirectly aid in more harmonious coexistence with other technologies in the unlicensed spectrum. Releases 16 of 3GPP [112] introduced the possibility of transmission and reception at multiple transmission and reception points on the network side, a mechanism called CoMP [132], where a device is transmitted via a variety of transmission points, which may switch between one another dynamically or be used collectively from several sites. Thus, providing URLLC services in NR-U with synchronized spectrum sharing and CoMP is viable.

In [133], extensive work is exhibited on the CoMP-Enabled NR-U for IOT Networks to improve the spectrum efficiency, address interference issues, and maximize the utilization of unlicensed spectrum. The authors propose a semi-distributed ADMM-BCU algorithm to address the joint

Fig. 14. Unlicensed access with synchronized and synchronized sharing (adapted from [129]).

beamforming coordination and user selection problem. This algorithm finds a suboptimal solution with limited information exchange among MNOs via the CoMP server. The theoretical analysis and results demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed algorithm for large-scale IoT scenarios. So, a question appears if it is possible to apply these methods on vehicular networks using the ITS messages.

Works such as [134] propose research on the small cell and unlicensed coexistence communication technology. Using the CoMP algorithms and LTE NR-U, it concluded that the best way to improve efficiency is to reuse the scarce radio bands to a maximum extent intelligently. Furthermore, a path is open to the future where it is vital to study new deployments of scenarios using the NR-U and Wi-Fi. It will permit the enabling technologies of connected users and study the behaviour of physical and MAC layers protocols.

The author in [135] proposes another solution based on the CoMP method, the JT-CoMP-based dynamic networks, fulfilling the user-specific latency needs while maintaining dependable connectivity despite mmWave radio channel uncertainty. This work achieved results that outperform the legacy methods while ensuring latency requirements.

In [132], the authors discussed the concept of Generalized Coordinated Multipoint (GCoMP) as a proactive and efficient resource management framework for 5G. This work explains how the diverse requirements in the networks can be addressed through coordinated collaboration. The GCoMP framework considers user requirements, network architecture, and CoMP scenarios to make decisions on schemes and coordinating clusters. This framework aims to be a proactive and efficient resource management framework for supporting user requirements such as reliability, latency, throughput, and security. This document has a fascinating aspect: the usage of this framework achieved the requirements for V2X. However, there is still much work to be done in this framework to become an optimized solution.

A summary of all the methods presented here can be analyzed in Table 12.

The advent of NR-U 5G technology heralds a transformative era in connectivity, particularly for private networks. Characterized by its multi-carrier capabilities and dynamic features, NR-U elevates network performance and lays the groundwork for pioneering applications. Among these, the support for ITS and the facilitation of hybrid positioning applications stand out as quintessential examples of its innovative potential. Transitioning from the discussion on the contributions of NR-U 5G networks to vehicular dynamics, it becomes imperative to delve into the role of network positioning within the expansive domain of vehicular communication and autonomous driving. This exploration underscores the pivotal role of NR-U 5G technology in enhancing the efficiency and effectiveness of these advanced systems, marking a significant leap forward in the journey towards intelligent transportation solutions.

4.5. Security concerns

Some research has been conducted on security for 5G-based V2X services, with [136,137] being notable examples. Confidentiality and authenticity of information is the primary focus of security concerns of private 5G V2X networks, which implies that every piece of information must be kept secure from alteration or being accessed by individuals with malicious intent. Security concerns extends to vehicle communications where the information pertaining to the vehicle's location, velocity and movements needs to be secure from tampering or modification. The 3GPP standards dictate the type of encryption protocols that should be adhered to while exchanging information in these kinds of networks. Also, it is imperative to have strict authentication and authorization frameworks in place. In the case of private 5G networks that are aimed at V2X communication, it is crucial that a Public Key Infrastructure (PKI) and certificate issuance are well integrated. This ensures that no unauthorized vehicles or [137] can compromise the

Table 12

Comparison of the Mechanisms of Interference Reduction in NR-U.

	Method	Description	Results
[124]	LBT (Listen Before Talk)	Ensures fair spectrum sharing and minimizes interference with other devices in unlicensed bands.	N/A
[124]	omniLBT, dirLBT, pairLBT,LBTswitch	Variations of LBT for interference management in NR-U.	N/A
[122]	LBT-based channel access procedures for NR-U/Wi-Fi indoor mmWave coexistence scenarios	Simulation-based evaluation of different LBT-based channel access procedures for NR-U/Wi-Fi coexistence.	Enhanced coexistence performance, improved QoS and fairness
[131]	ML-based channel allocation for interference fairness between Wi-Fi and NR-U	Proposal of an ML model for channel allocation to enhance interference fairness between Wi-Fi and NR-U.	Promising results for long synchronization periods
[134]	CoMP (Coordinated Multi-Point)	Synchronous spectrum sharing method to improve coverage, capacity, and performance in 5G networks.	Improved spectrum efficiency, reduced interference
[135]	JT-CoMP (Joint Transmission CoMP)	Dynamic network solution for user-specific latency requirements in the presence of mmWave radio channel uncertainty.	Outperformed legacy methods, met latency requirements
[132]	G-Comp (Group Coordinated Multi-Point)	Proactive and efficient resource management framework for addressing diverse requirements in 5G networks.	Proactive resource management, support user requirements
[133]	ADMM-BCU (Alternating Direction Method of Multipliers-Base Cluster User)	Semi-distributed algorithm for joint beamforming coordination and user selection in CoMP-enabled NR-U for IoT networks.	Suboptimal solution, effectiveness demonstrated

system by communicating with legitimate ones. Furthermore, private 5G V2X networks permit network configuration at a granular level, allowing operators to isolate and secure V2X data flows within the private network, reducing exposure to vulnerabilities.

However, Private 5G V2X networks which employ NR-U spectrum have their share of antagonistic factors. For instance, there are consequences posed by the interference that results of the usage of spectrum sharing in unlicensed bands (e.g., sharing 5G with WiFi spectrum). Jamming constitutes a threat in such surroundings, where malicious entities disrupt communication by overwhelming frequencies with noise. To reduce the effects of these attacks, private V2X networks use protocols that are designed for changing spectral environments, such as dynamic spectrum management, and other measures that favor the maintenance of networks and systems even when attacks are ongoing.

In contrast, Public 5G networks must balance the needs of V2X services with those of a broad user base and a wide variety of applications. As a result, there are limits as to how much these networks can be tailored to V2X, even with dedicated network slices, particularly in regards to the ability to rapidly push out updates or patches which can be especially useful in a high security environment. Moreover, public infrastructure is per definition shared and can cause problems when assuring data privacy due to the ownership and control over the data residing with the service provider limiting the level of isolation and

security for the V2X data. Private 5G networks offer advantages in data ownership and privacy, allowing operators to control data generated within the V2X ecosystem directly. This type of control enables stricter enforcement of data privacy policies, essential for compliance with privacy regulations like General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), and supports more secure handling of sensitive data. In addition, operating the private network reduces the dependency on remote data centers and multi-tenant environment, and the associated risk of exposing private data. This is the case of public 5G networks, that hold a larger customer base and service providers, where V2X data will overlap with other application data, which raises concerns over data breach or unwarranted access to data.

In relation to enhanced resilience, private networks are deployed in certain focal points such as highways or cities where V2X communication plays a significant role in traffic efficiency and safety. Focused on high performing environments, V2X private network providers should have the capability of having enough resources to respond quickly to specific threats or outages providing consistent service, unlike Public Networks, that might experience congestion in crowded areas which will limit the reliability of V2X services. Considering the fact that there is a variety of applications and diverse data types in public networks, the V2X traffic might not always be prioritized in handling, which might contribute to great lags and poor communication quality in circumstances when sending and receiving data almost immediately is crucial for vehicle safety purposes.

To summarize, private 5G networks for V2X operating in unlicensed spectrum seem to be the most suitable answer for interconnected vehicles due to the high level of control, flexibility and security that they can provide. They provide high level of protection, redundancy and data confidentiality which are some of the requirements for V2X supporting communication.

5. Challenges and solutions in V2X with private 5G networks to support precise positioning

Throughout this research, several critical insights have emerged that are instrumental for advancing highly automated and connected vehicle ecosystems. This section highlights the foundational technologies, protocols, and infrastructure essential for meeting the stringent requirements of V2X systems and autonomous driving using the above mentioned technologies.

In order to perform road vehicle cooperative maneuvers, such as platooning or lane merging, there will be cooperation between different technologies. Such maneuvers are safety-critical, and their efficiency requires continuously accurate absolute (between certain protection

levels, as illustrated in Fig. 15) and relative position, as well as velocity information with a real-time update rate.

The effectiveness of these maneuvers is contingent upon precise and efficient localization, which must meet stringent criteria for both absolute and relative positioning accuracy, as outlined by the author [138] in Tables 13 and 14. These requirements emphasize the necessity for real-time, high-fidelity data regarding vehicle position and velocity, especially as automation advances to SAE Level 3 and beyond. Maintaining such precise localization and situational awareness is vital for ensuring the smooth execution of cooperative maneuvers, as any lapse in data accuracy or latency can significantly impact both safety and operational efficiency.

The foundation of cooperative maneuvers lies in vehicular communication, enabled by ITS standards, including CAM and DENM, both defined by ETSI. CAM, periodically transmitted to convey vehicle state information such as position, speed, and heading, are essential for V2V communication. This exchange will ensure that all vehicles within proximity are continuously informed of each other’s precise location, thereby significantly enhancing cooperative road maneuvers’ safety and operational efficiency. The reliability of these CAMs depends on the robustness of the underlying communication networks, which must operate with minimal latency to support the demanding requirements of advanced driving automation. By integrating GNSS data, corrected through techniques like double differencing and fused with onboard sensor information, vehicles can achieve the required localization accuracy, even under adverse conditions such as urban canyons, tunnels, or multipath environments. Still, there is little mistrust that the primary source of position data will be GNSS, the robustness and availability can improve by combining GNSS with laser scanners [139,140], radar sensors [141,142], vision-based systems [143–145] or maps [146–148]. The CAM can typically include essential vehicle data, such as identification details (ID, type, role, and size), timestamp information (e.g., UTC), positional data (geographic coordinates with confidence bounds and heading), and kinematic parameters (speed, driving direction, yaw rate, and acceleration).

CAM messages are designed to communicate the vehicle’s current status at consistent intervals, whereas DENM messages are triggered by specific events to deliver crucial situational awareness about hazardous road conditions, unforeseen occurrences, or other pertinent environmental details that may influence driving choices. Instances that would activate a DENM encompass abrupt deceleration, an obstruction on the roadway, adverse weather circumstances, or a collision involving another vehicle in proximity. DENM include data on the type of station sending the message, a timestamp, event type (e.g., roadworks, stationary vehicle, or approaching emergency vehicle), lane position, and lane status (open or closed).

The synergistic relationship between these two messaging standards improves the collaborative and proactive functionalities of vehicles within a connected ecosystem. CAM messages offer a constant stream of information regarding vehicle dynamics, enabling adjacent vehicles to maintain a real-time understanding of traffic patterns,

Fig. 15. Localization protection levels for autonomous vehicles [138].

Table 13

Localization requirements for freeway/highway operation. This assumes minimum lane widths of 3.6 m and allowable speeds of up to 137 KM/H (85 MPH) [138].

Vehicle type	Lateral [m]	Accuracy (95%) Long. [m]	Vertical [m]	Lateral [m]	Alert limit Long. [m]	Vertical [m]
Mid-Size car	0.24	0.48	0.44	0.72	1.40	1.30
Full-Size car	0.23	0.48	0.44	0.66	1.40	1.30
Standard Pickup	0.21	0.48	0.44	0.62	1.40	1.30

Table 14

Localization requirements for local (urban and rural) roads. This assumes lanes 3.0 m wide with a minimum curvature of 20 m or 3.3 m wide with a minimum curvature of 10 m [138].

Vehicle type	Lateral [m]	Accuracy (95%) Long. [m]	Vertical [m]	Lateral [m]	Alert limit Long. [m]	Vertical [m]
Mid-Size car	0.15	0.15	0.48	0.44	0.44	1.40
Full-Size car	0.13	0.13	0.48	0.38	0.38	1.40
Standard Pickup	0.12	0.12	0.48	0.34	0.34	1.40

relative distances, and changes in velocity. DENM messages function as notifications for unforeseen or transient alterations in the road environment that require prompt consideration. Integrating these two message types enables vehicles to develop a predictive grasp of road dynamics while also maintaining a responsive ability to unexpected hazards.

Moreover, cooperative localization leverages V2V communication to refine positioning capabilities further. Each vehicle broadcasts its precise location data to neighboring vehicles, contributing to a collective perception of the driving environment. This process comprises three stages: the initial exchange of CAM messages, integrating relative positional data with GNSS estimates, and disseminating updated positional data to improve accuracy across all participating vehicles. The initial exchange of CAMs establishes a baseline of vehicular positions, while subsequent integration of GNSS and relative data allows error minimization through a cooperative approach, reducing individual sensor inaccuracies. Finally, the continued dissemination of refined positional data ensures that all vehicles benefit from enhanced accuracy, creating a networked awareness critical for safety-critical maneuvers such as merging, overtaking, or coordinated braking. This collaborative approach yields a more robust localization system compared to stand-alone onboard sensor solutions, particularly in scenarios involving occlusions, non-line-of-sight conditions, or high-density traffic situations where individual sensor limitations could otherwise lead to localization errors.

In contrast, non-cooperative sensing involves perception systems such as radar, lidar, and cameras, which must undergo a multi-step process encompassing measurement, detection, and classification. Compared to cooperative systems' more direct position availability, this layered approach introduces additional complexity. Specifically, the measurement phase entails extracting raw sensor data, including point clouds from lidar or radar reflections, followed by detection, wherein objects such as vehicles, pedestrians, or obstacles are identified within the sensor data. Subsequently, classification categorizes these detected objects, assigning attributes such as type, size, and movement behavior. While these sensors are indispensable for relative localization, they present limitations, including restricted range, limited field of view, and susceptibility to occlusions. These limitations become particularly challenging in complex environments, such as densely populated urban areas or during adverse weather conditions, where sensor performance may degrade significantly. Consequently, augmented with other sensors, GNSS becomes crucial to meet the rigorous localization requirements for SAE Level 3 and higher, ensuring robustness in various operational scenarios.

On top of this, the GNSS estimates can be significantly improved using double differences. In GNSS, the single difference technique involves one vehicle observing two satellites simultaneously, and the measurement of one satellite is differenced, i.e., subtracted, from the other. Double differencing refers to the formation of the difference between two single differences, where single differences are obtained by taking the difference between the measurements from two vehicles for

the same satellite. This concept is the key for meeting the localization requirements of automated driving. This implies that the vehicles exchange this information with each other through CAMs, which also have their stringent requirements. In [149], QoS requirements of CAM and DENM are mapped to PC5 QoS Indicator (PQI) values 23 and 90, respectively, as described in Table 15.

Unlike the direct availability of position information in cooperative localization approaches, non-cooperative systems such as radar, lidar, 3D cameras, and other vision-based systems undergo a multi-step process involving measurement, detection, and classification. The process unfolds as follows:

Measurement Step: This initial phase involves extracting raw measurement data from the signal using signal processing algorithms. This data manifests as a cloud of reflecting points for radar and laser scanners, whereas, for vision-based systems, it appears as one or several pixel matrices.

Detection Step: Subsequently, the raw measurement data undergo segmentation and clustering to delineate objects within the data. This critical phase transitions the raw data into identifiable objects within the system's field of view.

Classification Step: The final phase aims to categorize the detected objects into distinct classes, such as vehicles, bicycles, and pedestrians, facilitating the system's interaction with its environment by understanding the type of objects present.

These steps underscore the complexity inherent in non-cooperative localization systems, which, unlike their cooperative counterparts, rely on an extensive processing pipeline to derive actionable position information.

These sensors can potentially face several scenarios that constrain their operation, either because of a limited sensing area in terms of range or aperture or due to an obstacle that blocks line-of-sight, as illustrated in Fig. 16.

It becomes, therefore, evident that for highly automated driving, GNSS is a necessity, alongside other sensors, working together cooperatively as illustrated in Fig. 17: an ego vehicle receives (i) GNSS error corrections via 5G base station and (ii) GNSS data captured by other vehicles (e.g., satellite pseudo ranges, and more) and uses this data to perform error-free double differentiation. Performance accuracy under this scenario, as long as there is no strong multipath and non-line-of-sight from the satellites, can be as low as 10 cm. Data fusion with other sensors ensures accuracy when the car travels inside a tunnel or in a high multipath scenario, like a very dense urban area.

There are numerous options for data fusion computation methods, such as the Bayesian-based approach [151–154], Kalman Filters (regular, extended, or unscented) [155,156], Particle Filters [157–159] and Covariance Intersection (CI) [160,161].

SAE Level 3+ cars are expected to be equipped with all of these

Table 15

Standardized PQI to QoS characteristics mapping.

PQI	Resource	Packet delay	Packet error	Max data	Window	Services
23	Guaranteed Bit Rate (GBR)	100 ms	10–4	N/A	2000 ms	Information sharing for automated driving – between UEs or UE and Road Side Units (RSU)
90	Delay critical GBR	10 ms	10–4	2000 bytes	2000 ms	Cooperative collision avoidance Sensor sharing Video sharing

Fig. 16. Situations where a ranging sensor at the red ego vehicle has limited performance in estimating the relative position of the green target vehicle [150].

Fig. 17. Cooperative localization with both cooperative and non-cooperative sensors to enhance the positioning accuracy of the vehicle [162].

sensors that can estimate the location of a vehicle. These are summarized in Table 16.

GNSS has the significant advantage of the standard reference datum between adjacent vehicles, which is crucial for V2V operations. Also, it is the only sensor that supports lane identification, which is especially important for lane change maneuvers, entering/exiting highways, turning at intersections, and other cooperative maneuvers between vehicles. Furthermore, when referenced with a map (that uses the same datum), it becomes possible to support road class identification (highway, interstate, local road, pavement type). Of course, when in tunnels, it must be complemented with an Inertial Motion Sensor due to the lack of coverage.

Overall, for SAE 3+ and V2X operations, relative perception (lidar, camera, radar) must be complemented by (GNSS, Inertial measurement unit sensors (IMU), Map) and operate in cooperative localization via CAMs to meet the requirements listed under Tables 13 and 14.

As vehicles are in an inconstant move (i.e., with variable speeds), the

Table 16 Automated vehicle sensor characteristics.

	Sensor	Pros	Cons
Perception (Vehicle Reference Frame)	Radar	Good ranging accuracy	Cannot detect road markings Less effective in featureless areas Less effective in snow and darkness
	Lidar	Highly accurate ranging	
	Camera	Good object detection	
Absolute localization (Global Reference Frame)	HD map	Excellent accuracy (< 10 cm 95%)	Requires continuous updates
	Motion sensors		
	GNSS	Low cost Global availability and common reference between vehicles	Poor performance in tunnels

absolute position must be available at a high rate with very low latency. This is evidenced in Table 17, where it shows the needed requirements for safety applications, and in Table 18, the meaning for each value presented in it. The need for HD map complement also requires high bandwidth. All of this implies the requirements of proper underlying infrastructure supported by a technology that meets these latency and broadband requirements. Moreover, GNSS can not independently provide such accurate vehicular positioning. It requires real-time correction services and, in some cases, hybrid positioning with cellular techniques. 5G supports the latency and broadband requirements and GNSS correction services in near real-time in its specification [163] and cellular positioning techniques.

Fig. 18 details this: (i) vehicles receive DENM from the RSU and (ii) GNSS signals from GPS and/or Galileo satellites. This is followed by (iii) a 5G gNB transmitting satellite position corrections (e.g., the magnitude of the error of the satellite orbits) via the Uu interface. Then, (iv) the vehicles exchange GNSS data via CAM, through a PC5 link, to perform the GNSS double difference technique, which allows the vehicle to estimate its position with extremely high accuracy (below 10 cm).

The Uu interface, radio or air interface, sends wireless communication signals between the UE and the base station (gNB in 5G). The PC5 is defined in cellular networks, particularly in LTE-V2X and 5G-V2X. This link can be used in different access technologies, WiFi or 5G, and which one should be used is out of the scope of this article, as there is ample literature about this, such as [164] and also about hybrid solutions [165, 166]. Nonetheless, a 5G connection is needed to transmit data to a cloud or to provide GNSS corrections. V2X services in 5G can occur in the n38 and n47 bands, where the former concerns private networks and the latter belongs to the public operators. The licensed spectrum is minimal (only 50 MHz), meaning that sharing among a country's public MNO is impractical. This means there is a high likelihood that road operators and municipalities will set up their own 5G private networks using NR-U technologies and the n47 band to provide ITS services.

6. Lessons learned

Throughout this research, several critical insights have emerged that are instrumental for advancing highly automated and connected vehicle ecosystems. The following lessons highlight the foundational technologies, protocols, and infrastructure essential for meeting the stringent requirements of V2X systems and autonomous driving.

Private 5G networks are crucial for advancing autonomous driving within V2X communication and ITS. These networks support cooperative localization, where precise, real-time communication through CAM and DENM overcomes the limitations of individual vehicle sensors, providing a shared, accurate view of vehicle positions. The resilience of localization is further enhanced by integrating GNSS data with multi-sensor fusion—using IMUs, lidar, and radar—particularly valuable when GNSS signals weaken in dense environments.

Standards such as CAM and DENM, alongside the regulated use of unlicensed 5 GHz spectrum, enable these private networks to manage safety-critical V2X data reliably and in compliance with regulatory demands. Private 5G infrastructure will meet the bandwidth and low latency essential for real-time localization and maneuvering. Furthermore, hybrid localization approaches that combine GNSS with 5G positioning achieve sub-meter accuracy even in complex urban environments, making private 5G networks indispensable for the safe and efficient development of ITS and autonomous driving solutions.

This study emphasizes the necessity of combining cooperative localization, standardized communication protocols, and advanced 5G Private infrastructure to create a reliable ITS. This integrated approach supports autonomous driving and fosters a safer and more efficient transportation ecosystem, setting the stage for future developments in intelligent transportation.

Table 17
Technical requirements of safety-critical applications [167].

Applications	Horizontal accuracy	GNSS time accuracy	Position integrity	Position authentication	Continuity	Position fix rate	Vertical accuracy	Time to fix	Latency
Red light violation warning	1	1	3	2	3	2	1	2	2
Queue warning	2	1	3	3	1	2	1	2	2
Obstacles on the road	2	1	3	3	2	2	1	2	2
Work zone warning	2	1	2	2	2	2	1	2	2
Weather based hazards	2	1	2	2	2	2	1	2	2
Curve speed warning	2	1	3	3	2	2	1	2	2
Emergency electronic brake light	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2
Oversize vehicle warning	1	1	2	2	1	1	1	2	1
360° all around view	3	2	3	3	2	2	1	2	2
Blind spot lane change warning	1	1	3	3	2	2	1	2	2
Pedestrians in crossroads	2	1	3	3	2	2	1	2	2
Wrongway driving	3	2	3	2	3	2	2	2	2
Cooperative intersection collision avoidance including railways	3	3	3	3	3	3	2	2	3
Automatic speed limitation	2	1	2	3	2	2	1	2	2
Emergency brake assist system, forward collision avoidance	3	3	3	3	3	3	1	2	3
Automatic driving	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	2	3
Autonomous car	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
Synchronization	0	3	3	3	3	3	0	3	3

Table 18
Meaning of the values in Table 17. Acronyms: PL (protection level); IR (integrity risk); Pfa (probability of false alarm); PD (probability of detection).

Parameter	1	2	3
Horizontal accuracy	10 m	less than 10 m	values in Tables 13 and 14
GNSS time accuracy	1s	between 1 μ s and 1 s	less than 1 μ s
Position integrity	PL>25m at IR=10-4	PL<25m, at IR=10-4	PL<2.5m, at IR=10-6
Position authentication	: Pfa<10% and PD>68%	Pfa<1% and PD>75%	Pfa<0.2% and PD>85%
Continuity	low	medium	high
Position fix rate	1 Hz	between 1 and 20 Hz	higher than 20 Hz
Vertical accuracy	10 m	less than 10 m	values in Tables 13 and 14
Time to fix	30 s	less than 30 s	1.5 s
Latency	100 ms	between 20 and 100 ms	less than 20 ms

7. Conclusion

Exploring ITS and integrating private 5G networks for facilitating V2X communications, have revealed significant advancements and challenges in this dynamic field. This paper has systematically dissected the multifaceted aspects of ITS, highlighting the pivotal role of V2X communications in advancing automated driving systems and ensuring road safety.

Firstly, delineating specific spectrum bands for V2X communications, particularly the n38 and n47 bands, underscores the criticality of spectrum allocation in the effective deployment of ITS. The monopolistic tendencies arising from limited public spectrum availability highlight the need for a more equitable distribution of these resources. Importantly, the possibility of leveraging private networks for V2X operations opens avenues for more decentralized and versatile ITS implementations. However, it introduces challenges such as co-existence with other technologies and handovers between public and private networks.

The discussion on CAM and DENM elucidates how vehicular communication technologies contribute to the safety and efficiency of autonomous vehicles. These technologies facilitate the exchange of positional and environmental data and underscore the need for stringent quality and reliability standards in vehicular communications.

The challenges in meeting the Safety of Life (SoL) requirements for

Fig. 18. V2X interfaces for information exchange.

SAE Level 3+ autonomous vehicles are significant. While onboard sensors provide a foundation for vehicle perception, their limitations in the field of view and sensing range necessitate adopting cooperative localization techniques. The fusion of GNSS data, enhanced through methods like double differencing with data from other on-board sensors, forms a comprehensive approach to achieve the desired accuracy in vehicle localization.

In this scenario, the 5G technology emerges as a cornerstone in the evolution of ITS. Its capacity to support high bandwidth and low latency enables real-time services essential for advanced ITS applications. The development of private 5G networks, tailored for specific industrial needs, marks a significant step towards realising Industry 4.0, providing the necessary infrastructure for the seamless operation of autonomous vehicles and other real-time applications.

The architectural frameworks for deploying private 5G networks and the challenges and opportunities presented by different spectrum

allocation strategies, particularly NR-U, indicate both the complexity and potential of 5G in ITS. While the performance of NR-U may not surpass that of traditional NR in the licensed spectrum, it has an indisputable role in catering to specific business models and addressing the issue of spectrum saturation.

In conclusion, integrating ITS with private 5G networks presents a promising yet challenging frontier. The potential for enhanced safety, efficiency, and automation in road transport is vast, but it is accompanied by the need for robust solutions for spectrum allocation, network architecture, and addressing data communication challenges. As this field continues to evolve, it will be imperative to address these challenges through innovative approaches and continued research to realize a truly intelligent and interconnected transportation system.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Bruno Mendes: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Marco Araújo:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision. **Adriano Goes:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Investigation. **Daniel Corujo:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Investigation. **Arnaldo S.R. Oliveira:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

Bruno Mendes reports financial support was provided by Capgemini Engineering. Bruno Mendes reports a relationship with Capgemini Engineering that includes: employment. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

References

- [1] M. Boban, A. Kousaridas, K. Manolakis, J. Eichinger, and W. Xu, "Use cases, requirements, and design considerations for 5 g v2x," 2017. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1712.01754>.
- [2] M. Usman, M. Qaraqe, M.R. Asghar, A.A. Gebremariam, I.S. Ansari, F. Granelli, Q. H. Abbasi, A business and legislative perspective of v2x and mobility applications in 5 g networks, *IEEe Access*. 8 (2020) 67.426. –67 435.
- [3] C.R. Storck, F. Duarte-Figueiredo, A survey of 5 g technology evolution, standards, and infrastructure associated with vehicle-to-everything communications by internet of vehicles, *IEEe Access*. 8 (2020) 117.593. –117 614.
- [4] P. Wang, B. Di, H. Zhang, K. Bian, L. Song, Platoon cooperation in cellular v2x networks for 5 g and beyond, *IEEe Trans. Wirel. Commun.* 18 (8) (2019) 3919–3932.
- [5] V. Sharma, I. You, N. Guizani, Security of 5-g-v2x: Technologies, standardization, and research directions, *IEEE Network* 34 (5) (2020) 306–314.
- [6] J. Wang, J. Liu, N. Kato, Networking and communications in autonomous driving: A survey, *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials* 21 (2) (2019) 1243–1274.
- [7] Y. Cao, T. Griffon, F. Fahrenkrog, M. Schneider, F. Naujoks, F. Tango, S. Wolter, A. Knapp, Y. Page, J.L. Mallada et al., "L3pilot-code of practice for the development of automated driving functions," 2022.
- [8] "ii," 2021. [Online]. Available: <http://www.itu.int/pub/R-REG-RR>.
- [9] M.J. Khan, M.A. Khan, S. Malik, P. Kulkarni, N. Alkaabi, O. Ullah, H. El-Sayed, A. Ahmed, S. Turaev, Advancing c-v2x for level 5 autonomous driving from the perspective of 3 gpp standards, *Sensors* 23 (4) (2023) [Online]Available, <https://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/23/4/2261>.
- [10] M. Kutilla, K. Kauvo, P. Pyykönen, X. Zhang, V.G. Martinez, Y. Zheng, S. Xu, A c-v2x/5 g field study for supporting automated driving, in: 2021 IEEE Intelligent Vehicles Symposium (IV), 2021, pp. 315–320.
- [11] K.L. Chen, W.Y. Chen, R.H. Hwang, Optimizing resource allocation with high-reliability constraint for multicasting automotive messages in 5 g nr c-v2x networks, *IEEe Trans. Veh. Technol.* 72 (4) (2023) 4792–4804.
- [12] J. Andersen, S. Sutcliffe, Intelligent transport systems (its)- an overview, *IFAC Proceedings Volumes*, vol. 33, no. 18, pp. 99–106, 2000, in: IFAC Conference on Technology Transfer in Developing Countries: Automation in Infrastructure Creation (DECOM-TT 2000), Pretoria, South Africa, 2000, 5-7 July[Online] Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S147466701737129X>.
- [13] J. Maneros, M. Rondinone, A. Gonzalez, R. Bauza, and D. Krajewicz, "itetris platform architecture for the integration of cooperative traffic and wireless simulations," 01 2009.
- [14] ETSI, *Digital cellular telecommunications system (DCS); Radio Equipment; Harmonized EN covering the essential requirements of article 3.2 of Directive 2014/53/EU*, Std. ETSI EN 302 665, Jan 2016. [Online]. Available: https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_en/302600_302699/302665/01.01.01_60/en_302665v01010101p.pdf.
- [15] E. T. S. I. (ETSI), *Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS); Service architecture; Service types and Service realisation; Part 3: Vehicle-related services*, Std. ETSI EN 302 636 03, Feb 2020. [Online]. Available: https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_en/302600302699/30263603/01.01.02_20/en_30263603v01010102a.pdf.
- [16] D. Stepanova, T. Sukuvaara, V. Karsisto, Intelligent transport systems – road weather information and forecast system for vehicles, in: 2020 IEEE 91st Vehicular Technology Conference (VTC2020-Spring), 2020, pp. 1–5.
- [17] R.I. Meneguette, R.E. De Grande, A.A.F. Loureiro, Intelligent Transportation Systems, Springer International Publishing, Cham, 2018, pp. 1–21, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-93332-0_1 [Online]Available.
- [18] ITU, "Intelligent transport systems - handbook on land mobile (including wireless access) 2021 edition".
- [19] Z. Lv, W. Shang, Impacts of intelligent transportation systems on energy conservation and emission reduction of transport systems: A comprehensive review, *Green Technologies and Sustainability* 1 (1) (2023) 100002 [Online] Available, <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2949736122000021>.
- [20] K. Sjöberg, P. Andres, T. Buburuzan, A. Brakemeier, Cooperative intelligent transport systems in europe: Current deployment status and outlook, *IEEE Vehicular Technology Magazine* 12 (2) (2017) 89–97.
- [21] A. da República. Lei n.º 32/2013, de 10 de maio | dr. [Online]. Available: <http://diariodarepublica.pt/dr/detalhe/lei/32-2013-261161>.
- [22] J.R.P. Christidis, "Measuring road congestion," 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/bitstream/JRC69961/congestion%20report%20final.pdf>.
- [23] E. Parliament. Cooperative, connected and automated mobility (ccam). [Online]. Available: <https://transport.ec.europa.eu/transport-themes/intelligent-transport-systems/cooperative-connected-and-automated-mobility-ccam.en>.
- [24] I. Voungidis, L. Maglaras, A.S. Alfakheh, A.H. Al-Bayatti, M.A. Ferrag, Use of smartphones for ensuring vulnerable road user safety through path prediction and early warning: An in-depth review of capabilities, limitations and their applications in cooperative intelligent transport systems, *Sensors* 20 (4) (2020) [Online]Available, <https://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/20/4/997>.
- [25] J. Casademont, A. Calveras, D. Quinones, M. Navarro, J. Arribas, M. Catalan-Cid, Cooperative-intelligent transport systems for vulnerable road users safety, in: 2019 7th International Conference on Future Internet of Things and Cloud (FiCloud), 2019, pp. 141–146.
- [26] V. Maglogiannis, D. Naudts, S. Hadiwardoyo, D. van den Akker, J. Marquez-Barja, I. Moerman, Experimental v2x evaluation for c-v2x and its-g5 technologies in a real-life highway environment, *IEEE Transactions on Network and Service Management* 19 (2) (2022) 1521–1538.
- [27] I. Mavromatis, A. Tassi, R.J. Piechocki, Operating its-g5 dsrcc over unlicensed bands: A city-scale performance evaluation, in: 2019 IEEE 30th Annual International Symposium on Personal, Indoor and Mobile Radio Communications (PIMRC), 2019, pp. 1–7.
- [28] R. Sattiraju, D. Wang, A. Weinand, H.D. Schotten, Link level performance comparison of c-v2x and its-g5 for vehicular channel models, in: 2020 IEEE 91st Vehicular Technology Conference (VTC2020-Spring), 2020, pp. 1–7.
- [29] Its, "En 302 663 - v1.3.0 - intelligent transport systems (its); its-g5 access layer specification for intelligent transport systems operating in the 5 ghz frequency band," 2019.
- [30] Erm, "En 302 571 - v2.1.1 - intelligent transport systems (its); radiocommunications equipment operating in the 5 855 mhz to 5 925 mhz frequency band; harmonised standard covering the essential requirements of article 3.2 of directive 2014/53/eu," 2017. [Online]. Available: <https://portal.etsi.org/TB/ETSIDeliverableStatus.aspx>.
- [31] Its, "En 302 637-2 - v1.4.1 - intelligent transport systems (its); vehicular communications; basic set of applications; part 2: Specification of cooperative awareness basic service," 2019.
- [32] K. Ansari, Joint use of dsrcc and c-v2x for v2x communications in the 5.9 ghz its band, *IET Intelligent Transport Systems* 15 (2021) 213–224, 2[Online]Available, <https://ietresearch.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1049/itr2.12015>.

- [33] C. C. Consortium, "Car 2 car communication consortium white paper on its-g5 and sidelink lte-v2x co-channel coexistence mitigation methods about the c2c-cc," 2021.
- [34] TSGS, "Ts 123 502 - v15.2.0 - 5 g; procedures for the 5 g system (3 gpp ts 23.502 version 15.2.0 release 15)," 2018. [Online]. Available: https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_ts/123500_123599/123502/15.02.00_60/ts_123502v150200p.pdf.
- [35] TSGC, "Ts 124 571 - v16.1.0 - 5 g; 5 g system (5 gs); control plane location services (lcs) procedures; stage 3 (3 gpp ts 24.571 version 16.1.0 release 16)," 2020. [Online]. Available: https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_ts/124500_124599/124571/16.01.00_60/ts_124571v160100p.pdf.
- [36] TSGR, "Ts 138 305 - v16.1.0 - 5 g; ng radio access network (ng-ran); stage 2 functional specification of user equipment (ue) positioning in ng-ran (3 gpp ts 38.305 version 16.1.0 release 16)," 2020. [Online]. Available: https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_ts/138300_138399/138305/16.01.00_60/ts_138305v160100p.pdf.
- [37] R. Keating, M. Säily, J. Hukkoniemi, J. Karjalainen, Overview of positioning in 5 g new radio, in: 2019 16th International Symposium on Wireless Communication Systems (ISWCS), 2019, pp. 320–324.
- [38] R.S. Campos, Evolution of positioning techniques in cellular networks, from 2 g to 4 g, *Wireless Communications and Mobile Computing* 2017 (2017).
- [39] G. Cecchini, A. Bazzi, B.M. Masini, A. Zanella, Localization-based resource selection schemes for network-controlled lte-v2v, in: 2017 International Symposium on Wireless Communication Systems (ISWCS), 2017, pp. 396–401.
- [40] S. Dwivedi, R. Shreevastav, F. Munier, J. Nygren, I. Siomina, Y. Lyazidi, D. Shrestha, G. Lindmark, P. Ernström, E. Stare, S.M. Razavi, S. Muruganathan, G. Masini, Åke Busin, and F. Gunnarsson, "Positioning in 5 g networks," 2 2021. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2102.03361>.
- [41] TSGR, "Ts 138 455 - v15.0.0 - 5 g; ng-ran; nr positioning protocol a (nrppa) (3 gpp ts 38.455 version 15.0.0 release 15)," 2018. [Online]. Available: https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_ts/138400_138499/138455/15.00.00_60/ts_138455v150000p.pdf.
- [42] TSGC, "Ts 129 572 - v17.6.0 - 5 g; 5 g system; location management services; stage 3 (3 gpp ts 29.572 version 17.6.0 release 17)," 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://portal.etsi.org/TB/ETSIDeliverableStatus.aspx>.
- [43] H. Wymeersch, G. Seco-Granados, G. Destino, D. Dardari, F. Tufvesson, 5 g mmwave positioning for vehicular networks, *IEEE Wirel. Commun.* 24 (6) (2017) 80–86.
- [44] 3GPP, "Specification 23.700-86: Study on architecture enhancement to support ranging based services and sidelink positioning," 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://portal.3gpp.org/desktopmodules/Specifications/SpecificationDetails.aspx?specificationId=4008>.
- [45] 5GPP, "5 g ppp technology board & 5 g ia verticals task force empowering vertical industries through 5 g networks- current status and future trends," 2020. [Online]. Available: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3698113>.
- [46] TSGC, "Ts 124 501 - v16.5.1 - 5 g; non-access-stratum (nas) protocol for 5 g system (5 gs); stage 3 (3 gpp ts 24.501 version 16.5.1 release 16)," 2020. [Online]. Available: https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_ts/124500_124599/124501/16.05.01_60/ts_124501v160501p.pdf.
- [47] TSGR, "Ts 138 413 - v16.2.0 - 5 g; ng-ran; ng application protocol (ngap) (3 gpp ts 38.413 version 16.2.0 release 16)," 2020. [Online]. Available: https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_ts/138400_138499/138413/16.02.00_60/ts_138413v160200p.pdf.
- [48] F.A. Pinto, G. Santaromita, C. Fiandrino, D. Giustiniano, Characterizing location management function performance in 5 g core networks, *IEEE* 11 (2022) 66–71 [Online] Available, <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/9974927/>.
- [49] S. Bartoletti, H. Wymeersch, T. Mach, O. Brunnegård, D. Giustiniano, P. Hammarberg, M.F. Keskin, J.O. Lucruz, S.M. Razavi, J. Rönblom, F. Tufvesson, J. Widmer, N.B. Melazzi, Positioning and sensing for vehicular safety applications in 5 g and beyond, *IEEE Communications Magazine* 59 (11) (2021) 15–21.
- [50] F. Mogyorósi, P. Revisnyei, A. Pašić, Z. Papp, I. Törös, P. Varga, A. Pašić, Positioning in 5 g and 6 g networks—a survey, *Sensors* 22 (13) (2022) 4757, <https://doi.org/10.3390/s22134757>. Jun[Online]. Available.
- [51] C. Satya Ganesh Nutan Dev, L. Pathak, G. Ponnareddy, D. Das, Nrpos: A multi-rach framework for 5 g nr positioning, in: 2020 IEEE 3rd 5G World Forum (5GWF), 2020, pp. 25–30.
- [52] D. Li, X. Chu, L. Wang, Z. Lu, S. Zhou, X. Wen, Performance evaluation of e-cid based positioning on oai 5 g-nr testbed, in: 2022 IEEE/CIC International Conference on Communications in China (ICCC), 2022, pp. 832–837.
- [53] G. Shen, R. Zetik, R.S. Thoma, Performance comparison of toa and tdoa based location estimation algorithms in los environment, in: 2008 5th Workshop on Positioning, Navigation and Communication, 2008, pp. 71–78.
- [54] R. Dilli, Analysis of 5 g wireless systems in fr1 and fr2 frequency bands, in: 2020 2nd International Conference on Innovative Mechanisms for Industry Applications (ICIMIA), 2020, pp. 767–772.
- [55] J.H. Jo, J.N. Shim, Byoungnam, Kim, C.B. Chae, and D.K. Kim, "Aoa-based position and orientation estimation using lens mimo in cooperative vehicle-to-vehicle systems," 2023.
- [56] W. Guo, Y. Deng, C. Guo, S. Qi, J. Wang, Performance improvement of 5 g positioning utilizing multi-antenna angle measurements, *Satell. Navig.* 3 (2022) 1–14, 12[Online]. Available, <https://satellite-navigation.springeropen.com/articles/10.1186/s43020-022-00078-y>.
- [57] Z. Papp, G. Irvine, R. Smith, F. Mogyorósi, P. Revisnyei, I. Törös, A. Pašić, Tdoa based indoor positioning over small cell 5 g networks, in: NOMS 2022-2022 IEEE/IFIP Network Operations and Management Symposium, 2022, pp. 1–6.
- [58] P. Revisnyei, F. Mogyorósi, Z. Papp, I. Törös, A. Pašić, Performance of a tdoa indoor positioning solution in real-world 5 g network, in: NOMS 2023-2023 IEEE/IFIP Network Operations and Management Symposium, 2023, pp. 1–6.
- [59] A. Kakkavas, M.H. Castañeda Garcia, R.A. Stirling-Gallacher, J.A. Nossek, Multi-array 5 g v2v relative positioning: Performance bounds, in: 2018 IEEE Global Communications Conference (GLOBECOM), 2018, pp. 206–212.
- [60] J. Gante, L. Sousa, G. Falcao, Dethroning gps: Low-power accurate 5 g positioning systems using machine learning, *IEEE J. Emerg. Sel. Top. Circuits. Syst.* 10 (2) (2020) 240–252.
- [61] M. Cui, K. Zhao, Z. Zheng, M. Gu, Y. Wang, H. Pan, B. Wang, A novel iterative positioning method based on difference rss model with 5 g field experiments, *IEEE Sens. J.* (2023) 1–1.
- [62] M.T. Scott, T.J. Scott, V.G. Kelly, The validity and reliability of global positioning systems in team sport: a brief review, *The Journal of Strength & Conditioning Research* 30 (5) (2016) 1470–1490.
- [63] J. McNeff, The global positioning system, *IEEE Trans. Microw. Theory. Tech.* 50 (3) (2002) 645–652.
- [64] W. Lechner, S. Baumann, Global navigation satellite systems, *Comput. Electron. Agric.* 25 (1) (2000) 67–85 [Online]. Available, <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0168169999000563>.
- [65] P.M. Kintner, B.M. Ledvina, The ionosphere, radio navigation, and global navigation satellite systems, *Advances in Space Research* 35 (5) (2005) 788–811, fundamentals of Space Environment Systems. [Online]. Available, <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0273117705004667>.
- [66] E. S. Agency. Tiff - navipedia. [Online]. Available: <https://gssc.esa.int/navipedia/index.php/TFFF>.
- [67] I. R. (ed.), "Rinex the receiver independent exchange format." [Online]. Available: https://files.igs.org/pub/data/format/rinex_4.00.pdf.
- [68] O. Jonah, L. Lanctot, Tri-band multi-constellation gnss antenna, in: 2020 IEEE International Symposium on Antennas and Propagation and North American Radio Science Meeting, 2020, pp. 1935–1936.
- [69] J. Shi, Y. Gao, A comparison of three ppp integer ambiguity resolution methods, *GPS. Solut.* 18 (2014) 519–528, 10[Online]. Available, <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10291-013-0348-2>.
- [70] D. Odijk, A. Khodabandeh, N. Nadarajah, M. Choudhury, B. Zhang, W. Li, P. J. Teunissen, Ppp-rtk by means of s-system theory: Australian network and user demonstration, *J. Spat. Sci.* 62 (1) (2017) 3–27.
- [71] P. Hou, J. Zha, T. Liu, B. Zhang, Recent advances and perspectives in gnss ppp-rtk, *Measurement Science and Technology* (2023).
- [72] G. GNSS. The path to high gnss accuracy | galileo. [Online]. Available: <https://galileognss.eu/the-path-to-high-gnss-accuracy/>.
- [73] Geo++ Ssr vs. osr - geo++ | gnss technology. [Online]. Available: <https://www.geo++de/ssr-vs-osr/>.
- [74] G. Wübbena, J. Wübbena, T. Wübbena, M. Schmitz, Ssr technology for scalable real-time gnss applications, in: *IGSWorkshop*, 2017.
- [75] P.-J.G. Teunissen, A-ppp: Array-aided precise point positioning with global navigation satellite systems, *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing* 60 (6) (2012) 2870–2881.
- [76] J. Geng, Q. Zhang, G. Li, J. Liu, D. Liu, Observable-specific phase biases of wuhan multi-gnss experiment analysis center's rapid satellite products, *Satell. Navig.* 3 (2022) 1–15, 12[Online]. Available, <https://satellite-navigation.springeropen.com/articles/10.1186/s43020-022-00084-0>.
- [77] An assessment of the interoperability of ppp-ar network products, *The Journal of Global Positioning Systems* 15 (2017) 1–12. 2017 15:112[Online]. Available, <https://jgps.springeropen.com/articles/10.1186/s41445-017-0009-9>.
- [78] R. Hirokawa, I. Fernandez-Hernandez, S. Reynolds, Ppp/ppp-rtk open formats: Overview, comparison, and proposal for an interoperable message, *Navigation - Journal of The Institute of Navigation* (2021), 12.
- [79] J. Strandberg, T. Hobiger, R. Haas, Towards real-time gnss reflectometry using kalman filtering, in: *IGARSS 2018 - 2018 IEEE International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium*, 2018, pp. 2043–2046.
- [80] W. Chen, C. Yu, D. Dong, M. Cai, F. Zhou, Z. Wang, L. Zhang, Z. Zheng, Formal uncertainty and dispersion of single and double difference models for gnss-based attitude determination, *Sensors* 17 (2017) 408. 2017, Vol. 17, Page 4082[Online]. Available, [https://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/17/2/408](https://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/17/2/408/htmlhttps://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/17/2/408).
- [81] G. Li, J. Wu, C. Zhao, Y. Tian, Double differencing within gnss constellations, *GPS. Solut.* 21 (2017) 1161–1177, 7.
- [82] Y. Shu, P. Xu, X. Niu, Q. Chen, L. Qiao, J. Liu, High-rate attitude determination of moving vehicles with gnss: Gps, bds, glonass, and galileo, *IEEE Trans. Instrum. Meas.* 71 (2022).
- [83] L. Zhang, D. Hou, J. Zhang, Positioning performance based on integrated gnss network of vehicles, in: 2021 IEEE 9th International Conference on Information, Communication and Networks, ICIN 2021, 2021, pp. 278–286.
- [84] E. Falletti, G. Falco, V.H. Nguyen, M. Nicola, Performance analysis of the dispersion of double differences algorithm to detect single-source gnss spoofing, *IEEE Transactions on Aerospace and Electronic Systems* 57 (2021) 2674–2688, 10.
- [85] R.E. Kalman, A New Approach to Linear Filtering and Prediction Problems, *Journal of Basic Engineering* 82 (1) (1960) 35–45, <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.3662552>, 03[Online]. Available.
- [86] Q. Zhang, L. Zhao, L. Zhao, J. Zhou, An improved robust adaptive kalman filter for gnss precise point positioning, *IEEE Sens. J.* 18 (10) (2018) 4176–4186.
- [87] Y. Guo, S. Chai, L. Cui, Gnss precise point positioning based on dynamic kalman filter with attenuation factor, in: 2018 37th Chinese Control Conference (CCC), 2018, pp. 4734–4738.

- [88] G. Wang, Y. Han, J. Chen, S. Wang, Z. Zhang, N. Du, Y. Zheng, A gnss/ins integrated navigation algorithm based on kalman filter, in: 6th IFAC Conference on Bio-Robotics BIOROBOTICS 2018 51, 2018, pp. 232–237 [Online]. Available, <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2405896318312692>.
- [89] A.K. Baharom, S. Abdul-Rahman, R. Jamali, S. Mutalib, Towards modelling autonomous mobile robot localization by using sensor fusion algorithms, in: 2020 IEEE 10th International Conference on System Engineering and Technology (ICSET), 2020, pp. 185–190.
- [90] J. Geng, F.N. Teferle, X. Meng, A.H. Dodson, Towards ppp-rtk: Ambiguity resolution in real-time precise point positioning, *Advances in Space Research* 47 (2011) 1664–1673, 5.
- [91] J.A. Del Peral-Rosado, P. Nolle, S.M. Razavi, G. Lindmark, D. Shrestha, F. Gunnarsson, F. Kaltenberger, N. Sirola, O. Särkkä, J. Roström, K. Vaarala, P. Miettinen, G. Pojani, L. Canzian, H. Babaroglu, E. Rastorgueva-Foi, J. Talvitie, D. Flachs, Design considerations of dedicated and aerial 5 g networks for enhanced positioning services, in: 2022 10th Workshop on Satellite Navigation Technology (NAVITEC), 2022, pp. 1–12.
- [92] C. Rydholm and W. Pommer, “Hybrid positioning solution using 5 g and gnss,” 2021.
- [93] F. Li, R. Tu, L. Zeng, S. Zhang, M. Liu, X. Lu, Integrated positioning with double-differenced 5 g and undifferenced/double-differenced gps, *Measurement* 218 (2023) 113114 [Online]Available, <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0263224123006784>.
- [94] L. Bai, C. Sun, A.G. Dempster, H. Zhao, J.W. Cheong, W. Feng, Gnss-5 g hybrid positioning based on multi-rate measurements fusion and proactive measurement uncertainty prediction, *IEEe Trans. Instrum. Meas.* 71 (2022) 1–15.
- [95] J.A. del Peral-Rosado, O. Renaudin, C. Gentner, R. Raulefs, E. Dominguez-Tijero, A. Fernandez-Cabezas, F. Blazquez-Luengo, G. Cueto-Felgueroso, A. Chassaingne, D. Bartlett, F. Grec, L. Ries, R. Prieto-Cerdeira, J.A. Lopez-Salcedo, G. Seco-Granados, Physical-layer abstraction for hybrid gnss and 5 g positioning evaluations, in: 2019 IEEE 90th Vehicular Technology Conference (VTC2019-Fall), 2019, pp. 1–6.
- [96] J.A. del Peral-Rosado, F. Gunnarsson, S. Dwivedi, S.M. Razavi, O. Renaudin, J. A. López-Salcedo, G. Seco-Granados, Exploitation of 3d city maps for hybrid 5 g rtt and gnss positioning simulations, in: *ICASSP2020 - 2020 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing (ICASSP)*, 2020, pp. 9205–9209.
- [97] P. Zheng, X. Liu, T. Ballal, and T.Y. Al-Naffouri, “5 g-aided rtk positioning in gnss-deprived environments,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:2303.13067*, 2023.
- [98] Z. Abu-Shaban, G. Seco-Granados, C.R. Benson, H. Wymeersch, Performance analysis for autonomous vehicle 5 g-assisted positioning in gnss-challenged environments, in: 2020 IEEE/ION Position, Location and Navigation Symposium (PLANS), 2020, pp. 996–1003.
- [99] S. Saleh, A. Elmezayen, Q. Bader, M. Elhabiby, A. Noureldin, Would future mmwave wireless networks be an alternative positioning technique to gnss-based high precision positioning?, in: 2022 IEEE 95th Vehicular Technology Conference: (VTC2022-Spring), 2022, pp. 1–5.
- [100] E. Logota, D. Corujo, S. Jeon, J. Rodriguez, R.L. Aguiar, The 5G Internet, John Wiley & Sons, Ltd, 2015, pp. 29–62, ch. 2[Online]Available, <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/9781118867464.ch2>.
- [101] W. Jiang, B. Han, M.A. Habibi, H.D. Schotten, The road towards 6 g: A comprehensive survey, *IEEE Open J. Commun. Soc.* 2 (2021) 334–366.
- [102] 3GPP. Release 17. [Online]. Available: <https://www.3gpp.org/specifications-technologies/releases/release-17>.
- [103] 3GPP. Release 18. [Online]. Available: <https://www.3gpp.org/specifications-technologies/releases/release-18>.
- [104] P. Trakadas, L. Sarakis, A. Giannopoulos, S. Spantideas, N. Capsalis, P. Gkonis, P. Karkazis, G. Rigazzi, A. Antonopoulos, M.A. Cambeiro, S. Gonzalez-Diaz, L. Conceição, A cost-efficient 5 g non-public network architectural approach: Key concepts and enablers, building blocks and potential use cases, *Sensors* 21 (16) (2021) [Online]Available, <https://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/21/16/5578>.
- [105] C. Lai, R. Lu, D. Zheng, X. Shen, Security and privacy challenges in 5 g-enabled vehicular networks, *IEEE Network* 34 (2) (2020) 37–45.
- [106] L. Sarakis, P. Trakadas, J. Martrat, S. Prior, O. Trullols-Cruces, E. Coronado, M. Centenaro, G. Kontopoulos, E. Atxutegi, P. Gkonis, S. Gonzalez-Diaz, A. Antonopoulos, S. Siddiqui, P. Merino, Cost-efficient 5 g non-public network roll-out: The affordable5g approach, in: 2021 IEEE International Mediterranean Conference on Communications and Networking (MeditCom), 2021, pp. 221–227.
- [107] A. Alalewi, I. Dayoub, S. Cherkaoui, On 5 g-v2x use cases and enabling technologies: A comprehensive survey, *IEEe Access.* 9 (2021) 107.710. –107 737.
- [108] H. Frank, C. Colman-Meixner, K.D.R. Assis, S. Yan, D. Simeonidou, Techno-economic analysis of 5 g non-public network architectures, *IEEe Access.* 10 (2022) 70.204. –70 218.
- [109] A. Aijaz, Private 5 g: The future of industrial wireless, *IEEE Industrial Electronics Magazine* 14 (4) (2020) 136–145.
- [110] A. Rostami, Private 5 g networks for vertical industries: Deployment and operation models, in: 2019 IEEE 2nd 5G World Forum (5GWF), 2019, pp. 433–439.
- [111] M. Wen, Q. Li, K.J. Kim, D. López-Pérez, O.A. Dobre, H.V. Poor, P. Popovski, T. A. Tsiftsis, Private 5 g networks: Concepts, architectures, and research landscape, *IEEe J. Sel. Top. Signal. Process.* 16 (1) (2022) 7–25.
- [112] TSGS, “Tr 121 916 - v16.0.1 - digital cellular telecommunications system (phase 2+)(gsm); universal mobile telecommunications system (umts); lte; 5 g; release 16 description; summary of rel-16 work items (3 gpp tr 21.916 version 16.0.1 release 16),” 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://portal.etsi.org/TB/ETSI/ETSI/verivale/Status.aspx>.
- [113] 3GPP, “Tr 38.889 v16.0.0, study on nr-based access to unlicensed spectrum (release 16),” 2018–12. [Online]. Available: https://www.3gpp.org/ftp/tsg_ran/TSG_RAN.
- [114] S. Muhammad, H.H. Refai, M.O. Al Kalaa, 5 g nr-u: Homogeneous coexistence analysis, in: *GLOBECOM2020 - 2020 IEEE Global Communications Conference*, 2020, pp. 1–6.
- [115] R. Bajracharya, R. Shrestha, H. Jung, Future is unlicensed: Private 5 g unlicensed network for connecting industries of future, *Sensors* 20 (10) (2020) 2774.
- [116] A. H. S, A. K. R, B. Gullapalli, Digital transformation of oil & gas fields architecting multi-services digital private network on 5 g nr-u model, in: 2022 IEEE Wireless Antenna and Microwave Symposium (WAMS), 2022, pp. 1–5.
- [117] J. Oh, Y. Kim, Y. Li, J. Bang, J. Lee, Expanding 5 g new radio technology to unlicensed spectrum, in: 2019 IEEE Globecom Workshops (GC Wkshps), 2019, pp. 1–6.
- [118] R.K. Saha, Coexistence of cellular and iee 802.11 technologies in unlicensed spectrum bands - a survey, *IEEE Open J. Commun. Soc.* 2 (2021) 1996–2028.
- [119] A. Khlass, D. Laselva, Efficient handling of small data transmission for rrc inactive ues in 5 g networks, in: 2021 IEEE 93rd Vehicular Technology Conference (VTC2021-Spring), 2021, pp. 1–7.
- [120] M. Hirzallah, M. Krunz, B. Kecioglu, B. Hamzeh, 5 g new radio unlicensed: Challenges and evaluation, *IEEe Trans. Cogn. Commun. Netw.* 7 (3) (2021) 689–701.
- [121] T. Inoue, 5 g nr release 16 and millimeter wave integrated access and backhaul, in: 2020 IEEE Radio and Wireless Symposium (RWS), 2020, pp. 56–59.
- [122] S. Lagen, L. Giupponi, S. Goyal, N. Patriciello, B. Bojovic, Demir, M. Beluri, New radio beam-based access to unlicensed spectrum: Design challenges and solutions, *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials* 22 (1) (2020) 8–37.
- [123] J. Choi, V. Marojevic, C.B. Dietrich, J.H. Reed, S. Ahn, Survey of spectrum regulation for intelligent transportation systems, *IEEe Access.* 8 (2020) 140.145. –140 160.
- [124] G. Naik, J.M. Park, J. Ashdown, W. Lehr, Next generation wi-fi and 5 g nr-u in the 6 ghz bands: Opportunities and challenges, *IEEe Access.* 8 (2020) 153.027. –153 056.
- [125] S.Y. Lien, D.J. Deng, C.C. Lin, H.L. Tsai, T. Chen, C. Guo, S.M. Cheng, 3 gpp nr sidelink transmissions toward 5 g v2x, *IEEe Access.* 8 (2020) 35.368. –35 382.
- [126] Z. Ali, S. Lagén, L. Giupponi, R. Rouil, 3 gpp nr v2x mode 2: Overview, models and system-level evaluation, *IEEe Access.* 9 (2021) 89.554. –89 579.
- [127] FCC. Federal register: Unlicensed national information infrastructure (u-nii) devices in the 5 ghz band. [Online]. Available: <https://www.federalregister.gov/d/2014-09279>.
- [128] Anacom, “Station license exemption,” January 3, 2023. [Online]. Available: https://www.anacom.pt/streaming/IsencaoLicencaDeEstacao_Rev3jan2023.pdf?contentId=1188499&field=ATTACHED_FILE.
- [129] Y. Wei and X. Zhang, “How does unlicensed spectrum feature in the upcoming release from 3 gpp?”
- [130] S. Lagen, L. Giupponi, N. Patriciello, Lbt switching procedures for new radio-based access to unlicensed spectrum, in: 2018 IEEE Globecom Workshops (GC Wkshps), 2018, pp. 1–6.
- [131] S. Szott, K. Kosek-Szott, A.Lo Valvo, I. Tinnirello, Using self-deferral to achieve fairness between wi-fi and nr-u in downlink and uplink scenarios, *Comput. Commun.* 193 (2022) 176–188 [Online]. Available, <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0140366422002420>.
- [132] M.S.J. Solajia, H. Salman, A.B. Kihero, M.I. Sağlam, H. Arslan, Generalized coordinated multipoint framework for 5 g and beyond, *IEEe Access.* 9 (2021) 72.499. –72 515.
- [133] Q. Chen, K. Yang, H. Jiang, M. Qiu, Joint beamforming coordination and user selection for comp-enabled nr-u networks, *IEEe Internet. Things. J.* 9 (16) (2022) 14.530. –14 541.
- [134] V. Sathya, S.M. Kala, K. Naidu, Heterogenous networks: From small cells to 5 g nr-u, *Wirel. Pers. Commun.* 128 (2023) 2779–2810, 2[Online]Available, <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11277-022-10070-z>.
- [135] D. Kumar, S.K. Joshi, A. Tölli, Latency-aware highly-reliable mmwave systems via multi-point connectivity, *IEEe Access* 10 (2022) 32.822. –32 835.
- [136] T. Yoshizawa, D. Singelee, J.T. Muehlberg, S. Delbruel, A. Taherkordi, D. Hughes, B. Preneel, A survey of security and privacy issues in v2x communication systems, *ACM Comput. Surv.* 55 (9) (2023), <https://doi.org/10.1145/3558052>. Jan [Online]. Available.
- [137] R. Sedar, C. Kalalas, F. Vázquez-Gallego, L. Alonso, J. Alonso-Zarate, A comprehensive survey of v2x cybersecurity mechanisms and future research paths, *IEEE Open Journal of the Communications Society* 4 (2023) 325–391.
- [138] T. Reid, S. Houts, R. Cammarata, G. Mills, S. Agarwal, A. Vora, G. Pandey, Localization requirements for autonomous vehicles, *SAE Int. J. Connect. Autom. Vehicles* 2 (3) (2019) 173–190.
- [139] A. Soloviev, Tight coupling of gps, laser scanner, and inertial measurements for navigation in urban environments, in: 2008 IEEE/ION Position, Location and Navigation Symposium, 2008, pp. 511–525.
- [140] J.H. Im, S.H. Im, G.I. Jee, Vertical corner feature based precise vehicle localization using 3d lidar in urban area, *Sensors* 16 (8) (2016) [Online]. Available, <https://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/16/8/1268>.
- [141] D. Vivet, P. Checchin, R. Chapuis, Localization and mapping using only a rotating fmcw radar sensor, *Sensors* 13 (4) (2013) 4527–4552 [Online]. Available, <https://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/13/4/4527>.

- [142] F. de Ponte Müller, E.M. Diaz, I. Rashdan, Cooperative infrastructure-based vehicle positioning, in: 2016 IEEE 84th Vehicular Technology Conference (VTC-Fall), 2016, pp. 1–6.
- [143] J. Laneurit, C. Blanc, R. Chapuis, L. Trassoudaine, Multisensor data fusion for global vehicle and obstacles absolute positioning, in: IEEE IV2003 Intelligent Vehicles Symposium. Proceedings (Cat. No.03TH8683), 2003, pp. 138–143.
- [144] M. Schreiber, H. Königshof, A.M. Hellmund, C. Stiller, Vehicle localization with tightly coupled gnss and visual odometry, in: 2016 IEEE Intelligent Vehicles Symposium (IV), 2016, pp. 858–863.
- [145] M.A. Olivares-Mendez, J.L. Sanchez-Lopez, F. Jimenez, P. Campoy, S.A. Sajadi-Alamdari, H. Voos, Vision-based steering control, speed assistance and localization for inner-city vehicles, *Sensors* 16 (3) (2016) [Online]. Available, <https://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/16/3/362>.
- [146] R. Toledo-Moreo, D. Betaille, F. Peyret, J. Laneurit, Fusing gnss, dead-reckoning, and enhanced maps for road vehicle lane-level navigation, *IEEE J. Sel. Top. Signal. Process.* 3 (5) (2009) 798–809.
- [147] Y. Jiang, H. Qiu, M. McCartney, G. Sukhatme, M. Gruteser, F. Bai, D. Grimm, R. Govindan, Carloc: Precise positioning of automobiles, in: *Proceedings of the 13th ACM Conference on Embedded Networked Sensor Systems*, ser. SenSys '15, Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 2015, pp. 253–265, <https://doi.org/10.1145/2809695.2809725> [Online]. Available.
- [148] F. Jiménez, S. Monzón, J.E. Naranjo, Definition of an enhanced map-matching algorithm for urban environments with poor gnss signal quality, *Sensors* 16 (2) (2016) [Online]. Available, <https://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/16/2/193>.
- [149] TSGS, “Ts 123 287 - v16.3.0 - 5 g; architecture enhancements for 5 g system (5 gs) to support vehicle-to-everything (v2x) services (3 gpp ts 23.287 version 16.3.0 release 16),” 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://portal.etsi.org/TB/ETSIDeliverableStatus.aspx>.
- [150] F. De Ponte Müller, Survey on ranging sensors and cooperative techniques for relative positioning of vehicles, *Sensors* 17 (2) (2017) [Online]. Available, <https://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/17/2/271>.
- [151] A. Bahr, M.R. Walter, J.J. Leonard, Consistent cooperative localization, in: 2009 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation, 2009, pp. 3415–3422.
- [152] S. Roumeliotis, G. Bekey, Distributed multirobot localization, *IEEE Trans. Robot. Autom.* 18 (5) (2002) 781–795.
- [153] A.H. Sakr, G. Bansal, Cooperative localization via dsrc and multi-sensor multi-target track association, in: 2016 IEEE 19th International Conference on Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITSC), 2016, pp. 66–71.
- [154] R. Madhavan, K. Fregene, L. Parker, Distributed heterogeneous outdoor multi-robot localization, in: *Proceedings 2002 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (Cat. No.02CH37292)* 1, 2002, pp. 374–381, vol.1.
- [155] F. Bounini, D. Gingras, H. Pollart, D. Gruyer, Real time cooperative localization for autonomous vehicles, in: 2016 IEEE 19th International Conference on Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITSC), 2016, pp. 1186–1191.
- [156] H. Li, F. Nashashibi, Cooperative multi-vehicle localization using split covariance intersection filter, in: 2012 IEEE Intelligent Vehicles Symposium, 2012, pp. 211–216.
- [157] F. Caron, M. Davy, E. Duflos, P. Vanheeghe, Particle filtering for multisensor data fusion with switching observation models: Application to land vehicle positioning, *IEEE Transac. Signal Process.* 55 (6) (2007) 2703–2719.
- [158] A. Howard, Multi-robot simultaneous localization and mapping using particle filters, *Int. J. Rob. Res.* 25 (12) (2006) 1243–1256, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0278364906072250> [Online]. Available.
- [159] M. Montemerlo, S. Thrun, D. Roller, B. Wegbreit, Fastslam 2.0: An improved particle filtering algorithm for simultaneous localization and mapping that provably converges, in: *Proceedings of the 18th International Joint Conference on Artificial Intelligence*, ser. IJCAI'03, Morgan Kaufmann Publishers Inc., San Francisco, CA, USA, 2003, pp. 1151–1156.
- [160] L. Chen, P. Arambel, R. Mehra, Estimation under unknown correlation: covariance intersection revisited, *IEEE Trans. Automat. Contr.* 47 (11) (2002) 1879–1882.
- [161] F. Seeliger, K. Dietmayer, Inter-vehicle information-fusion with shared perception information, in: 17th International IEEE Conference on Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITSC), 2014, pp. 2087–2093.
- [162] D. Yoon, “Cooperative perception for social driving in connected vehicle traffic,” PhD thesis, Clemson University, 2021.
- [163] TSGR, “Ts 138 305 - v17.0.0 - 5 g; ng radio access network (ng-ran); stage 2 functional specification of user equipment (ue) positioning in ng-ran (3 gpp ts 38.305 version 17.0.0 release 17),” 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://portal.etsi.org/TB/ETSIDeliverableStatus.aspx>.
- [164] V. Mannoni, V. Berg, S. Sesia, E. Perraud, A comparison of the v2x communication systems: Its-g5 and c-v2x, in: 2019 IEEE 89th Vehicular Technology Conference (VTC2019-Spring), 2019, pp. 1–5.
- [165] Z.H. Mir, J. Toutouh, F. Filali, Y.B. Ko, Enabling dsrc and c-v2x integrated hybrid vehicular networks: Architecture and protocol, *IEEE Access.* 8 (2020) 180.909–180.927.
- [166] K. Ansari, Joint use of dsrc and c-v2x for v2x communications in the 5.9 ghz its band, *IET Intelligent Transport Syst.* 15 (2) (2021) 213–224 [Online]. Available, <https://ietresearch.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1049/itr2.12015>.
- [167] “Report on road users needs and requirements” European Union Agency for the Space Programme, Report GSA-MKD-RD-UREQ- 250283, 2021.